

1 **In Search of an Integrative Method to Study Unconscious Processing: An Application of**
2 **Bayesian and General Recognition Theory Models to the Processing of Hierarchical**
3 **Patterns in the Absence of Awareness.**

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Abstract

The dissociation between conscious and unconscious perception is one of the most relevant issues in the study of human cognition. While there is evidence suggesting that some stimuli might be unconsciously processed up to its meaning (e.g., high-level stimulus processing), some authors claim that most results on the processing of subliminal stimuli can be explained by a mixture of methodological artefacts and questionable assumptions about what can be considered non-conscious. Particularly, one of the most controversial topics involves the method by which the awareness of the stimuli is assessed. To address this question, we introduced an integrative approach to assess the extent to which masked hierarchical stimuli (i.e., global shapes composed of local elements) can be processed in the absence of awareness. We combined a priming task where participants had to report global or local shapes, with the use of subjective and objective awareness measures collected either in a separate block (offline), or trial-by-trial during the main task (online). The unconscious processing of the masked primes was then evaluated through two different novel model-based methods: a Bayesian and a General Recognition Theory modeling approach. Despite the high correlation between awareness measures, our results show that the use of alternative approaches based on different theoretical assumptions leads to diverging conclusions about the extent of the unconscious processing of the masked primes.

62 1. Introduction

63 The scientific study of consciousness is not only one of the most relevant and hot topics in the
64 current scientific scene, it is also arguably one of the last frontiers in human knowledge (Block,
65 2002; Chalmers, 2003; Dennett, 2002; Graziano, 2019, 2022; Jimenez et al., 2024; Lau, 2022). Over
66 the recent years, the field has witnessed an exponential growth in the research volume devoted to it
67 and its applications (Michel et al., 2019), and also the proliferation of a number of theories from
68 different fields such as philosophy, psychology, neurosciences, physics or even mathematics, which
69 have tried to explain the problem of subjective experience (Northoff & Lamme, 2020; Seth &
70 Bayne, 2022). Within consciousness research, and particularly in the field of cognitive science, one
71 of the most controversial and debated issues refers to the study of unconscious processing and the
72 dissociation between conscious and nonconscious perception (Rothkirch et al., 2022; Rothkirch &
73 Hesselmann, 2017; Shanks et al., 2021; Vadillo et al., 2022). The main disagreement stems from
74 the degree to which participants' behavior may be affected by information that is not consciously
75 accessed (Breitmeyer, 2015; Yaron et al., 2023). Interestingly, the field has been characterized by a
76 pendulum-like swing with respect to the scope of unconscious processing, with some researchers
77 arguing in favor of high-level unconscious processes (Biderman et al., 2020; Mudrik et al., 2014;
78 Soto et al., 2011), while others argue that most of the unconscious processing findings could be
79 explained by some pervasive methodological issues, along with certain widespread erroneous
80 assumptions when interpreting the results (Newell & Shanks, 2014; Shanks et al., 2021; Vadillo et
81 al., 2022).

82 According to these criticisms, a crucial challenge when inferring the presence of unconscious
83 processing is related to the way in which the awareness of the allegedly unconscious stimuli is
84 measured (Jimenez et al., 2024; Sandberg et al., 2010; Timmermans & Cleeremans, 2015). Although
85 several heterogeneous methods has been proposed to measure the contents of consciousness, they
86 might be divided according to two independent axes, namely the objective-subjective, and the
87 online-offline dimensions (Jimenez et al., 2024; Seth et al., 2008; Timmermans & Cleeremans,
88 2015). First, awareness measures can be divided into *objective* and *subjective* (Jimenez et al., 2024;
89 Persuh, 2018). Objective or performance-based measures typically involve instructing the
90 participants to discriminate between two different stimuli, usually through a two-alternative forced-
91 choice task (i.e., 2AFC¹). Sensitivity (d') to the task is then taken as a bias free measure (independent

¹ A 2AFC task refers to a task in which the observer is presented with two alternative stimuli simultaneously (or sequentially in a two-interval forced choice, 2IFC task) and forced to choose one based in a previously instructed criterion. Although the term is sometimes used in a more loosely form to describe a task where the subject views a single stimulus and must perform one of two responses, this use is not correct and has been discouraged by multiple authors (Hautus, 2015; Hautus et al., 2021; Schneider & Parker, 2009). It is important

92 of the response criterion) of the awareness of the stimuli: if individuals can discriminate between
93 the two stimuli ($d' > 0$), then they must have been aware of them. As the absence of awareness is
94 equated to the absence of performance in the prime discrimination task, unconscious processing is
95 demonstrated by the indirect influence of the unconscious stimuli over subsequent processing (e.g.,
96 priming effects). Although objective measures became the “gold standard” in consciousness
97 research until the mid-1980s, they have been criticized on many different grounds. The first is the
98 absence of exclusiveness, in other words, the $d' = 0$ criteria may rule out also unconscious
99 perception. The second also stems from the $d' = 0$ criteria, as it means to assume that the absence
100 of evidence for any conscious processing is taken as evidence of absence (Timmermans &
101 Cleeremans, 2015). The third, and perhaps most obvious, is that objective measures do not actually
102 estimate conscious experience, but only task performance (Lau, 2007), which also means that, in
103 principle, any device that performs above chance in the discrimination task (e.g., a photodiode)
104 would be consciously perceiving the stimuli (Persuh, 2018). On the other hand, subjective or
105 experience-based measures rely on the introspective reports of the individuals, which are directly
106 related to their phenomenal experiences (Overgaard et al., 2010; Persuh, 2018; Sandberg et al.,
107 2010). Specifically, different types of subjective measures have been proposed in consciousness
108 research, from the visibility (either dichotomous or graded) reports, including the PAS scale
109 employed in the present study, to different metacognitive measures (e.g., confidence ratings, post-
110 decision wagering; see Jimenez et al., 2024 for a thorough review on the topic of measuring
111 conscious experience). When assessing awareness in this way, participants are usually asked to
112 report their conscious perception of the stimulus on a dichotomous, graded, or even a continuous
113 scale (Pournaghdali et al., 2023; Ramsøy & Overgaard, 2004; Sergent & Dehaene, 2004). This
114 procedure is thought to be a more direct approach to the study of (un)conscious perception, as the
115 evidence for the existence of unconscious processing is obtained directly from the “no visibility”
116 reports of the participants. However, subjective measures have also been questioned on different
117 fronts. Major criticisms involve their susceptibility to response biases (Eriksen, 1960; Merikle et al.,
118 2001) and criterion confounds² (Bachmann, 2015; Kahneman, 1968). Particularly, shifts to a more

to note that our paradigm does not include the presence of two simultaneous stimuli and, therefore, does not constitute a 2AFC task (see Hautus, 2015 for an analysis of the implications of the use of a 2AFC task on the estimation of d'). Therefore, we will use the terms ‘prime discrimination task’ and ‘probe discrimination task’ to refer to the tasks employed in the present study.

² The criterion content problem was first introduced by Kahneman (1968) to highlight that observers base their perceptual (or metacognitive) decisions on a given set of features, which may not necessarily be the ones relevant to the task. This leads to the criterion content fallacy: concluding that observers are conscious of the task-relevant features only because they are conscious of something (Michel, 2023).

119 conservative or liberal response criterion could bias participants' reports of awareness, even within
120 the same experiment when different tasks are employed (Jimenez et al., 2020, 2023).

121 Second, we can also operatively classify awareness measures into the *online* and *offline* dimension,
122 according to the point in time at which they were obtained (Jimenez et al., 2024; Kiefer et al., 2023).

123 Offline (e.g., retrospective) measures of awareness include any type of measurement that is taken
124 once an ongoing task has been completed. Studies following this approach typically ask participants
125 to assess stimulus awareness in a separate block following the main task. Therefore, offline
126 measures (whether objective or subjective) do not interfere with task performance (e.g., the priming
127 task in a dissociation paradigm). However, their retrospective nature raises the concern of
128 "retrospective assessment" (Shanks & John, 1994) or the "immediacy problem" (Newell & Shanks,
129 2014), which highlight the need to assess consciousness concurrently, or as soon as possible after the
130 behavior. In addition, offline measures have faced further criticism due to their lack of sensitivity
131 to intra-individual fluctuations in visual awareness over trials (Bengson & Hutchison, 2007;
132 Lähteenmäki et al., 2015). Alternatively, online (e.g., concurrent) measures involve assessing
133 participants' awareness on a trial-by-trial basis during the task at hand, typically (although not
134 always) through subjective measures like the PAS scale (e.g., Jimenez et al., 2023; Kiefer et al.,
135 2023; Sabary et al., 2020). The introduction of online measures allows to examine potential intra-
136 individual fluctuations during the task, and meeting the immediacy criterion proposed by Newell
137 and Shanks (2014). However, online measures are not free of some problems, especially in those
138 tasks collecting reaction times (e.g., a priming paradigm) since they become dual-task paradigms.
139 As a consequence, the need to allocate attentional resources to two different tasks slows down the
140 responses to the main task and increases the variability of the reaction times (Jimenez et al., 2023;
141 Kiefer, Harpaintner, et al., 2023). The reliability and sensitivity of the assessment of stimulus
142 awareness is also affected (Newell & Shanks, 2014), as online measures usually induce a more
143 conservative awareness criterion bias due to the higher attentional demands of the dual-task design
144 (Jimenez et al., 2023).

145 Regardless of the different measures and points in time in which the awareness of a stimulus can be
146 assessed, another major issue in the field of consciousness research involves the way in which the
147 different measures of awareness are analyzed and interpreted within a given paradigm. This has led
148 to a wide variety of analysis strategies and criteria for differentiating between conscious and
149 unconscious processing (Jimenez et al., 2024; Timmermans & Cleeremans, 2015). In one of the
150 most widely adopted approaches, the classical dissociation paradigm, the strategy consists of
151 analyzing the differences between an indirect performance measure (e.g., priming measure) and an
152 awareness measure (Reingold & Merikle, 1988). Typically, this kind of strategy has been associated

153 with objective and offline measures of awareness (i.e., a forced-choice discrimination task aimed to
154 provide an objective index of stimulus visibility). If the awareness measure indicates chance level
155 discrimination of the stimuli, then we can conclude that any effect found in the indirect performance
156 measure is caused by the unconscious processing (Jimenez et al., 2023; Sabary et al., 2020). The
157 main theoretical assumption behind this paradigm is that the sensitivity measure in the
158 discrimination task (usually d') is an index of the stimulus level of awareness. The problems
159 associated with this approach include the acceptance of this theoretical a priori, along with the issues
160 related to the use of an offline-objective measure of awareness, especially the possibility that the
161 effects found may be due to the influence of a few conscious trials, even when the average
162 performance in the awareness measure is at chance level ($d' = 0$). To overcome this problem, some
163 studies have made use of post hoc data selection (see Rothkirch et al., 2022 for a review) in which
164 participants who are above a specific cut-off (typically chance-level in the objective awareness task)
165 are removed from the data, and only the remaining subset of “unaware” participants enter the data
166 analysis. Then, any effect found in this subset of participants is taken as supporting unconscious
167 perception. However, this procedure has been discouraged as it produces a *regression to the mean*³,
168 which introduces bias as the measurement error is not randomly sampled within the sub-group
169 (Rothkirch et al., 2022; Shanks, 2017). One possible alternative way to overcome this problem is
170 the use of regression methods, in which there is no need of selecting a non-conscious sub-group of
171 participants (in fact, they deliberately establish conditions that allow a proportion of subjects to
172 perform above chance in the awareness measure). Particularly, Greenwald et al. (1995) proposed a
173 regression-based method to predict unconscious effects from objective awareness measures (e.g.,
174 d'), in a linear regression model where the regression intercept represents the predicted effect for an
175 ideal observer whose awareness in the objective forced-choice measure is equal to zero.
176 Unfortunately, although the regression method proposed by Greenwald et al. (1995) avoids the post-
177 hoc selection of participants, it does not solve the source of the problem⁴. As it was the case with
178 the post-hoc selection of a subgroup of participants, the presence of measurement error in the
179 predictor variable (the awareness measure) leads to underestimating the slope coefficient. This is a

³ The statistical phenomenon of regression to the mean refers to the fact that due to the post hoc selection of a sub-sample of participants (double-dipping), the expected measurement error is no longer random. Instead, selecting the subgroup with the lowest awareness scores increases the probability of underestimation of awareness, as errors are expected to be biased towards the upper end of the awareness level.

⁴ In fact, the regression method was not originally intended to overcome the post-hoc selection problem, but to address other problems related to the demonstration of the existence of unconscious processing by indirect methods, specifically the assumptions made for the direct measures, a detailed explanation of which is beyond the scope of this paper (see Greenwald et al., 1995). However, since it allows avoiding post-hoc selection of participants, it has been used by other authors for this purpose (Goldstein et al., 2022; Klauer et al., 1998).

180 well-established issue known as regression attenuation or dilution (a phenomenon equivalent from
181 a psychometric point of view to the regression to the mean discussed above), that usually involves
182 the overestimation of the regression intercept. Indeed, further studies showed that this method
183 overestimates unconscious effects due to the underestimation of the regression slope (Doshier, 1998;
184 Sand & Nilsson, 2016). In response to this problem, some authors have proposed different solutions
185 to deal with the problem of measurement error and regression attenuation (Klauer et al., 1998;
186 Matzke et al., 2017). Specifically, Goldstein et al. (2022) recently developed a Bayesian generative
187 model solution for estimating the intercept of the regression model while accounting for the
188 measurement error. The authors build upon a Bayesian general method to correct for measurement
189 error in the estimation of correlations developed by Matzke et al. (2017), and adapt their model to
190 the particular case of unconscious processing, in order to estimate the intercept in a regression model
191 while accounting for error in the awareness and the effect measures.

192 Alternatively, and also within the priming paradigm, other studies have introduced online-subjective
193 reports to concurrently measure participants' awareness (Sabary et al., 2020; Van den Bussche et
194 al., 2013). The trial-by-trial awareness assessment allows to analyze conscious and unconscious
195 trials separately, thus meeting the immediacy criterion proposed by Newell and Shanks (2014), but
196 they are subjected to all of the criterion problems commented earlier, including biases and shifts
197 within and between subjects and tasks (see Jimenez et al., 2020 for a review). Importantly,
198 irrespective of the methodological issues, the use of subjective measures within the priming
199 paradigm introduces a change of theoretical assumptions in unconscious processing research. From
200 task accuracy as a measure of awareness to the use of subjective phenomenological reports to
201 identify unconscious trials, thus shifting from equating awareness to performance, to linking
202 consciousness with the sensitivity to a feature that *feels like something* for the participant. The
203 question therefore arises as to the extent to which both are comparable, or even whether the objective
204 and subjective thresholds of awareness measure the same underlying construct (Jimenez et al., 2023;
205 Kiefer, Harpaintner, et al., 2023; Sandberg et al., 2010; Song et al., 2015; Szczepanowski & Pessoa,
206 2007).

207 Outside the dissociation paradigm the question has become even more complicated. Usually, these
208 studies involve a masked detection/discrimination and/or categorization task in which awareness is
209 evaluated following one of the different methods described above. For example, subjective-offline
210 measures are employed in studies in which participants are required to discriminate or categorize
211 masked stimuli and, after completing the task, are asked to indicate (via subjective report) whether
212 they saw the stimuli (Juruena et al., 2010; Killgore & Yurgelun-Todd, 2004). Others have employed
213 subjective-online measures, assessing the awareness of the stimulus after each trial either through

214 dichotomous or graded judgments, and first order (visibility) or second order (metacognitive)
215 reports (Jimenez et al., 2018, 2021; Pournaghdali et al., 2023; Sandberg & Overgaard, 2015; Song
216 et al., 2015). Interestingly, in many of these works the interpretation of the sensitivity measures (i.e.,
217 d') is reversed, from being a measure of the degree of awareness (therefore assuming the necessity
218 of a $d' = 0$ to conclude the presence of unconscious processing) to being a measure of performance
219 in the -allegedly unconscious- task, thus assuming that a $d' = 0$ indicates the absence of processing
220 of the stimuli whether conscious or unconscious. From this last perspective, Pournaghdali et al.
221 (2023) conducted a recent study to analyze the relationship between perceptual processing and
222 awareness in which they collected online-subjective awareness measures while participants had to
223 discriminate between the emotional expression of masked face stimuli. To analyze the existence of
224 unconscious processing of the emotional expressions Pournaghdali et al. employed a novel method
225 based on the General Recognition Theory (GRT), a multivariate extension of the signal detection
226 theory (SDT), adapted to situations in which stimuli vary in more than one dimension, in this case
227 emotional valence and awareness (see also Ashby & Soto, 2015 for a detailed revision of the GRT).
228 Fitting this model allowed the authors to construct sensitivity vs awareness (SvA) curves that specify
229 the sensitivity (d') for emotional expression discrimination as a function of the relative likelihood
230 of awareness (RLNA). Thus, in this approach the presence of some level of sensitivity ($d' > 0$) when
231 the RLNA is high is an indicative of unconscious processing. Once again, and beyond the
232 methodological issues described, the question is whether these diverse paradigms and measures to
233 study non-conscious processing are assessing the same phenomena, or at least if they produce
234 comparable results across tasks and measures, a question that has been previously raised by some
235 authors (Jimenez et al., 2023, 2024; Kiefer, Frühauf, et al., 2023; Michel, 2023; Szczepanowski &
236 Pessoa, 2007).

237 To address these questions, in the present study we aim to explore unconscious visual processing
238 through an integrative paradigm that includes objective and subjective measures of awareness
239 collected both during the main task (online) and in separate blocks (offline). In addition, we will
240 examine unconscious processing through the different classical analysis strategies associated with
241 various combinations of awareness measures and research paradigms (e.g., dissociation paradigm,
242 trial-wise post-hoc selection), together with some new approaches recently proposed by different
243 authors and based on models derived from Bayesian analysis and General recognition theory
244 (Goldstein et al., 2022; Pournaghdali et al., 2023).

245 To this end, we will focus on the unconscious processing of non-hierarchical patterns formed by the
246 perceptual grouping of individual stimuli into a global form, and to what extent the local elements
247 and the global shape formed by their arrangement can occur outside the observer's awareness

248 (Jimenez et al., 2017, 2023; Koivisto & Revonsuo, 2004; Sabary et al., 2020). The question of which
249 processes are involved in perceptual organization has been extensively debated for decades
250 (Peterson & Kimchi, 2013; Wagemans, Elder, et al., 2012; Wagemans, Feldman, et al., 2012), but
251 the interplay between perceptual organization and visual awareness is still not well understood.
252 Classical cognitive theories assume that perceptual grouping (as part of the perceptual organization
253 process) can occur preattentively in the absence of attention (Julesz, 1981; Neisser, 1967; Treisman,
254 1985), and at least some types of perceptual grouping along with other perceptual organization
255 phenomena (e.g., contour integration, illusory contour completion) have been found in subliminal
256 processing conditions (Jimenez & Montoro, 2018; Jimenez et al., 2017; Lamy et al., 2006; Montoro
257 et al., 2014; Russell & Driver, 2005). However, the current evidence seems to depend on: (1) the
258 perceptual organizational processes under study, something that seems reasonable given that
259 perceptual organization comprises a multiplicity of processes with different time courses,
260 developmental trajectories and attentional demands (Kimchi, 2009; Sabary et al., 2020); and (2) the
261 methods employed to prevent the stimulus from entering consciousness (Moors et al., 2016).
262 Indeed, previous evidence on the integration of local elements into global shapes in the absence of
263 awareness already exists (Jimenez et al., 2023; Sabary et al., 2020) and, crucially for our interest,
264 this evidence derives from a variety of awareness measures and different analysis strategies. For
265 example, Sabary et al. (2020) explored the integration of local elements into a global shape in the
266 absence of awareness by combining a masked priming paradigm and online-subjective measures, in
267 which subjective awareness reports were obtained in a trial-by-trial basis using the Perceptual
268 Awareness Scale (PAS) developed by Ramsøy and Overgaard (2004). The authors concluded that
269 the local elements were represented in the absence of visual awareness, but conscious processing
270 was necessary for grouping them into a global shape. On the contrary, in a recent study, Jimenez et
271 al. (2023) expanded these findings by introducing two different masked priming paradigms in which
272 objective (offline) and subjective (PAS scale, both online and offline) awareness measures were
273 collected. Interestingly, the authors implemented a Bayesian regression model previously employed
274 by Goldstein et al. (2022) to predict the priming effect for ideal observers whose awareness is at
275 chance level, thus trying to overcome the limitations of the post-hoc selection of participants and
276 trials, typical of studies that use objective and subjective measures of awareness. Interestingly, the
277 combined results of these two studies showed local unconscious priming effects when assessed
278 through subjective-online measures of awareness (Sabary et al., 2020) and the unconscious
279 integration of local elements can be grouped into a global shape when measured through objective-
280 offline measures of awareness and analyzed through Bayesian regression models.

281 However, even though these two studies and, especially, the work by Jimenez et al. (2023) is an
282 example of the integration of different measures combined with multiple task conditions, still suffer
283 from the absence of some specific awareness measures and analysis strategies. Specifically, the
284 authors did not collect objective online measures of awareness, nor did they analyzed the
285 unconscious processing of the primes directly, beyond the indirect measures derived from the
286 masked priming (dissociation) approach. Also, in the case of Jimenez et al. (2023) they did not
287 investigate local priming effects. Therefore, in the present work we expand the paradigm devised
288 by Jimenez et al. (2023) by including objective awareness measures in a trial-by-trial manner
289 (online), along with a new model-based analysis of the association between the subjective measures
290 of awareness and the perceptual processing of the masked primes, based on the multidimensional
291 version of the signal detection theory (GRT). Moreover, both local and global priming effects were
292 analyzed. Particularly, we conducted four experiments focused on the role of awareness in
293 processing the local and global structure of hierarchical patterns, employing a classical masked
294 priming design with hierarchical stimuli similar to the ones employed by (Jimenez et al., 2023;
295 Sabary et al., 2020), to explore the unconscious processing of local and global primes using three
296 alternative approaches: the classical dissociation paradigm, and the two newly proposed Bayesian
297 and General Recognition Theory models. We implemented an exhaustive design in which objective
298 and subjective, as well as offline and online measures of awareness were combined, allowing us a
299 thorough comparison of the prime sensitivities (d') and indirect priming effects for the different
300 combinations of awareness measures. In the first two experiments, global shapes (squares or
301 diamonds) made of neutral (i.e., non-related to de global forma) local elements (triangles and
302 circles) were presented as primes in a masked priming paradigm. In the two remaining experiments,
303 an array of local elements (squares or diamonds) forming a neutral (i.e., non-related to the identity
304 of the local elements) global shape (triangles and circles) were presented as primes in the same
305 masked priming paradigm. All four experiments included three different blocks, each one associated
306 to a different task: (1) a single-task priming block where participants gave speeded responses to the
307 probe identity (which could be congruent or incongruent with the prime) while ignoring the primes;
308 (2) a multiple-task priming block in which besides responding to the probes, participants were asked
309 to indicate the identity of the prime (objective-online awareness measure) and to give a visibility
310 report using the PAS scale (subjective-online awareness measure), so participants had to attend to
311 the prime and the probe simultaneously within the same trial; and (3) a visibility block where
312 participants ignored the probe and the objective and subjective awareness measures of the prime
313 were collected offline (separate from the priming task). Note that the inclusion of three different
314 tasks also entails three distinct levels of attention to the prime, which allowed us to explore how

315 attention modulates the way in which the primes were processed, a relevant issue considering the
316 ongoing debate between proponents of theories of consciousness that equate attention to
317 consciousness (Dehaene et al., 2006), and those who dissociate both processes (Koch & Tsuchiya,
318 2007; Lamme, 2003). In addition, as the prime duration and specially the SOA between the prime
319 and the backward mask has proven to be a relevant factor in constructing the global shape under no
320 awareness conditions (Jimenez et al., 2017, 2023; Sabary et al., 2020), we introduced two different
321 SOAs (40 and 53 ms) in each priming condition (global / local) that produced divergent results in
322 previous studies. Finally, we also incorporated two minor but relevant improvements over the
323 previous studies already discussed (Jimenez et al., 2023; Sabary et al., 2020). First, to improve the
324 implementation of the GRT-based model, we doubled the number of catch trials to 64 (20% of the
325 total number of trials). Second, we matched the stimuli presentation conditions across all blocks by
326 including the probe stimulus also in the visibility block, even though participants were not required
327 to respond to it.

328 According to the results of previous works, we expected slower RTs in the multiple-task compared
329 to the single-task condition, due to the need to divide the attention between the primes and the probes
330 in the former. Crucially, we expected this attentional split to increase the variability of the RTs and
331 affect the facilitation (congruency) effects in the priming task, thus eliminating or at least attenuating
332 any possible unconscious priming effects in the multiple-task compared to the single-task condition.
333 Regarding the prime/mask SOA, we expected an increase in the priming effects as the SOA
334 increases, in line with previous studies showing that the total time that the prime is available for its
335 perceptual processing is a crucial factor in determining unconscious effects. Finally, we also
336 expected a higher level of unconscious processing of primes during the visibility block, due to the
337 higher level of attention paid to the primes compared to the multiple-block.

338 Regarding the visibility of the primes during the different blocks, we anticipated higher values in
339 the awareness measures during the visibility block, compared to the multiple-task block, given the
340 higher level of attention allocated to the primes during that block.

341 Previous mixed evidence about the extent to which objective and subjective measures of awareness
342 are assessing the same underlying process, with some studies pointing to the existence of a clear
343 dissociation (Szczepanowski & Pessoa, 2007), whereas others showing a high degree of
344 convergence between them (Jimenez et al., 2023; Kiefer et al., 2023) . Here, we expected a high
345 correlation between objective and subjective measures within the same block, and between the same
346 measure across different blocks, considering that previous studies employing the same paradigm
347 have found significant overlaps between the two different measures.

348

349 **2. Methods**

350 **2.1. Participants**

351 All participants were recruited among the population of undergraduate Psychology students at
352 UNED (all aged between 19 and 62). All reported normal or corrected-to-normal vision and received
353 course credit as reward for their participation. Sample size was calculated according to a mixed
354 sample stopping rule (Jimenez et al., 2023; Rouder, 2014; Schönbrodt et al., 2017) based on both a
355 minimum of participants and the cumulative evidence in favor or against the null hypothesis⁵. Once
356 the minimum number of participants ($n = 20$) per experiment had been reached, the final number of
357 participants in each experiment was calculated by monitoring the Bayes Factor (BF) values obtained
358 in the Bayesian regression analyses (Goldstein et al., 2022) at the end of each experimental day
359 (Matzke et al., 2015). Particularly, the data collection was stopped once we obtained “substantial”
360 evidence favoring either the null model (regression intercept = 0, $BF_{01} \leq 1/3$) or the alternative
361 model (regression intercept $\neq 0$, $BF_{10} \geq 3$), according to the classification scheme for the Bayes
362 factor developed by Jeffreys (1998). All the experiments were conducted after obtaining the written
363 consent of each participant, were in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and accepted by
364 the UNED ethics committee.

365 **2.2 Apparatus**

366 All the stimuli were displayed 19-in. LCD–LED Samsung 943N color monitor with a 75-Hz refresh
367 rate, a 5:4 aspect ratio, and a resolution of 1280 x 1024. The experiments were controlled by a
368 computer running E-Prime 3.0 software (Psychology Software Tools, 1996–2018). Viewing
369 distance was kept constant at approximately 57 cm. Participants performed their responses by means
370 of a keyboard and a mouse connected to the computer. All experiments were conducted in
371 soundproofed experimental cabins under controlled lighting and temperature conditions.

372 **2.3 Stimuli**

373 The stimuli were displayed at the center of the screen against a gray background (RGB: 70, 70, 70;
374 3.3 cd/m^2). All the experiments included four different primes. In the global priming condition, the
375 primes consisted of two global squares or diamonds, made up of twelve local x-cross or triangles.
376 In the local priming condition, the primes consisted of two global circles or triangles made up of
377 twelve diamonds or squares. The side of the global diamond subtended 6° , the side of the global

⁵ Specifically, we tested a minimum of 20 participants per experiment, corresponding to 2560 observations per condition, which exceeds the minimum observations per condition recommended by Brysbaert and Stevens (2018) for properly powered reaction time experiments.

378 square subtended 5° , the diameter of the global circle subtended 5.5° , and the side of the global
379 triangle subtended 5.5° . Each local element, either a square, a diamond, a triangle, or a x-cross
380 subtended $1.7^\circ \times 1.7^\circ$. All the contours of the local elements were 3 pixels wide (see **Figure 1a** and
381 **Figure 1b**). The probes consisted of twelve square or diamond-shaped stimuli with different visual
382 features (see **Figure 1c**). All the probes were light gray (RGB: 190, 190, 190; 33 cd/m^2) and smaller
383 than the probes to avoid retinotopic effects. Square probes subtended $3^\circ \times 3^\circ$, and diamond probes
384 subtended $4^\circ \times 4^\circ$.

385 The forward and backward mask were the same employed previously by Sabary et al. (2020) and
386 Jimenez et al. (2023). They consisted of 100 randomly placed light gray lines (RGB: 190, 190, 190;
387 33 cd/m^2) against a dark gray (RGB: 70, 70, 70; 3.3 cd/m^2) background color subtending a $7.5^\circ \times$
388 7.5° visual area. Background colored lines were superimposed over light gray lines to create random
389 noise patterns (i.e., line cuts). Each line subtended 1° - 1.5° visual angle in length and 4 pixels in
390 width. All the line orientations were randomly sampled, excluding 45° and its multiples to avoid any
391 potential response facilitation by the local elements of the mask (see **Figure 1d**). A pool of 50 masks
392 was created and randomly presented (only once per trial) during the experiment.

393

394 **Figure 1.** Stimuli used in the four experiments. (a) Prime stimuli for global priming experiments. (b) Prime
 395 stimuli for local priming experiments. (c) Probe stimuli for all the experiments. (d) Examples of mask stimuli.

396 **2.4. Design and procedure**

397 Four different and independent samples of participants took part in this study (one for each
 398 experiment). Each of the four experiments consisted of three different blocks in which participants
 399 performed three different tasks (one per block): (1) a single-task priming block, a multiple-task
 400 priming block, and a prime visibility block. In Experiments 1 and 2 (global priming condition) a
 401 global diamond or square shape made of neutral (circle or triangle) elements was presented as prime
 402 stimuli. In experiments 3 and 4 (local priming condition) a global (circle or triangle) neutral shape
 403 made of squares or diamond elements was presented as prime stimuli (see Figures 1 and 2). The
 404 participants that took part in each of the experiments performed the three blocks sequentially with
 405 a short break in between, during which the experimenters gave the participants the instructions for
 406 the next block. The experimental session started either with the single-task priming block or the
 407 multiple-task priming block, which were counterbalanced across participants within each

408 experiment. Last, after both priming blocks, the participants performed the visibility task block to
409 avoid any possible underestimation of the prime awareness due to increases in prime visibility
410 throughout the experiment (Timmermans & Cleeremans, 2015). In the single and multiple-task
411 priming blocks, each trial started with a fixation cross ($1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ light grey cross: RGB 210, 210, 210;
412 49 cd/m^2) displayed at the center of the screen for 1000 ms. Then, a forward mask was presented
413 for 100 ms, and followed by a prime that remained in the screen for 40 ms. In Experiments 1 and 3
414 (global and local priming conditions respectively), a backward mask pattern was presented for 67
415 ms immediately after the disappearance of the prime. In Experiments 2 and 4 (also global and local
416 priming conditions respectively), a blank inter stimulus (ISI) screen will be displayed for 13 ms
417 after the prime. Afterwards, the backward mask pattern was presented for 53 ms, in order to maintain
418 a constant 107 ms prime-target SOA across experiments. Finally, the probe remained on the screen
419 until response or at least 2000ms. In all experiments, during blocks one and two (single and multiple
420 tasks counterbalanced), participants were required to discriminate the shape of the probe presented
421 (square or diamond) as fast as possible but without making too many errors by pressing the buttons
422 1 and 2 of the numeric keypad on the right side of the keyboard with the index and middle finger of
423 the right hand. During the task, the index and middle fingers of the right hand were in constant
424 contact with the corresponding keys on the numeric keypad to ensure that the participant provided
425 speed responses to the probe stimuli. Before the beginning of the single-task priming block, the
426 participants were informed of the presence of the masked primes but were told to ignore them as
427 they were task irrelevant. After the participants consigned their response to the probe, an intertrial
428 blank screen appeared for 800 ms before the beginning of the next trial. In the multiple-task priming
429 block, the trial sequence was identical to the single-task priming block except that, following the
430 response to the probe discrimination task, a question mark was displayed on the screen signaling
431 the participants to provide both a subjective and an objective report of prime visibility. Both
432 subjective and objective judgments were collected simultaneously, by means of two different scales
433 PAS scales ranging from 1 to 4 (1 = No perception, 2 = Weak perception, 3 = Almost Clear
434 perception and 4 = Clear perception) mapped to the left (*Q, W, E, R* keys) and right (*U, I, O, P* keys)
435 sides of the keyboard. To perform their prime visibility responses, participants were instructed to
436 use the left PAS scale to indicate the visibility of the prime if they think it was a square, and to use
437 the right PAS scale whenever they think the prime presented was a diamond. Therefore, both the
438 objective judgment (shape discrimination) and the subjective judgment (visibility) were collected
439 simultaneously with a single keystroke without time pressure using the left hand, to avoid any
440 possible interference between the speeded probe discrimination task, and the prime shape
441 discrimination and visibility tasks. Participants were explicitly informed that the four categories of

442 the PAS scale referred exclusively to the perception of the global shape of the prime in the global
443 priming condition (Experiments 1 and 2) and to the perception of the local elements in the local
444 priming condition (Experiments 3 and 4), to ensure that participants only informed about the
445 awareness of the relevant dimension/content in each experiment. The specific instructions regarding
446 the Global PAS (Experiments 1 and 2) were: (1) ‘No perception’: There is no subjective experience
447 of the stimulus; (2) ‘Weak perception’: A feeling that some global figure has been shown although
448 this could not be identified, (3) ‘Almost clear perception’: Global shape perceived with some degree
449 of uncertainty. A feeling of almost being certain about one’s answer; (4) ‘Clear experience’: An
450 experience of clearly seeing the global shape. Complete certainty about one’s answer. The specific
451 instructions regarding the local PAS (Experiments 3 and 4) were: (1) ‘No perception’: There is no
452 subjective experience of the stimulus; (2) ‘Weak perception’: A feeling that some local elements
453 have been shown although they could not be identified, (3) ‘Almost clear perception’: local elements
454 perceived with some degree of uncertainty. A feeling of almost being certain about one’s answer;
455 (4) ‘Clear experience’: An experience of clearly seeing the local elements. Complete certainty about
456 one’s answer.

457 In the prime visibility block participants first performed a forced-choice prime shape discrimination
458 task, followed by a subjective report of the visibility of the prime on the PAS scale. In this block the
459 sequence of events was identical to single-task priming block except that, in this block, after the
460 offset of the second mask, two response options were displayed (“square” and “diamond”) on the
461 center of the screen until the participants provide their objective and subjective reports of the
462 visibility of the prime, following the same method described for the multiple-task block (two
463 different scales PAS scales ranging from 1 to 4 mapped to the left and right sides of the keyboard.
464 In this block, participants were explicitly instructed to ignore the probes and focus only on the
465 masked primes, trying to identify them as accurately as possible. They were also told to guess on
466 trials in which they could not identify the primes (and to give a PAS rating of 1 in those cases).
467 Trials were self-administered to ensure that participants were as ready to detect the primes as
468 possible.

469
470 **Figure 2.** Sequence of events in each block of the experiments.

471

472 **Table 1.** Priming condition and variable display durations (ISI and SOA) in ms across experiments.

Experiment	Priming condition	Variable display durations		Prime-target SOA
		ISI	Backward mask	
1	Global	0	67	107
2	Global	13	53	107
3	Local	0	67	107
4	Local	13	53	107

473

474 Each block consisted of 320 trials, of which 20% (64 trials) were catch trials in which no prime was
475 presented on the screen. Before the start of the experimental phase, participants performed 24
476 practice trials (single and multiple-task priming blocks), or 12 practice trials (prime visibility block).
477 Feedback was provided during the practice trials in the single and multiple-task priming blocks, but
478 not in the prime visibility block. Two breaks within each block (after trials – and --) and two more
479 between blocks (after block 1 and 2) were introduced to avoid fatigue effects. The breaks between
480 blocks were also used to brief the participants with instructions for the next phase. The whole
481 experimental session lasted about 90 minutes (including breaks within and between blocks).

482 **2.5. Data analyses**

483 Before the data analysis, incorrect trials (only for RT analyses), and trials with RTs below 200 ms
484 and above 2000 ms, and those above and below 2 standard deviations (*SD*) from the mean of each
485 participant (calculated after removing trials above 200 and below 2000 ms) were removed from the
486 analyses. In addition, participants with accuracy levels lower than 75% and/or more than 10% “clear
487 perception” subjective reports ($PAS = 4$) for catch trials in either the multiple-task priming block or
488 the prime visibility block were also excluded from the analyses. All the analyses reported were
489 conducted independently for each of the four experiments, so all variables manipulated were within-
490 subjects’ factors. The Bayesian generative modeling correction to the Greenwald regression method
491 (Goldstein et al., 2022; Greenwald et al., 1995), and the General Recognition Theory (GRT) model-
492 based analysis of the association between awareness and perceptual processing (Ashby & Soto,
493 2015; Pournaghdali et al., 2023), were performed employing Rstudio (version 2023.09.1+494, based
494 on the R programming language version 4.3.2) using the *rjags* (Plummer et al., 2006) and a modified
495 version of the *grtools* (Soto et al., 2017) packages respectively. All the remaining analyses were
496 performed using JASP statistical software (version 0.18.3, www.jasp-stats.org)⁶.

497 The hypothesis that local elements can be grouped together into global shapes (experiments 1 and
498 2), and that the local elements themselves can produce a reliable priming effect (experiments 3 and
499 4) in the absence of visual awareness, was tested separately for the single-task priming block, the
500 multiple-task priming block, and the prime visibility block, following complementary approaches.
501 In addition, to compare the results (RTs) from the single-task and the multiple-task blocks we
502 performed complementary analysis (2 x 2 Bayesian repeated-measures ANOVA, with block: single-
503 task vs multiple-task, and congruency: congruent vs incongruent as within-subject factors) that can
504 be found in the supplementary materials. In the case of the single-task priming block, data were
505 analysed by means of two different methods: (1) the classical dissociation paradigm (Reingold &
506 Merikle, 1988); and (2) a Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression
507 method (Goldstein et al., 2022). First RT data were sent to a Bayesian paired samples t-test
508 comparing congruent vs incongruent trials. Bayes factor (BF) provided evidence in favour or against
509 the existence of a priming effect by the masked primes. To estimate the degree to which the
510 participants were able to discriminate the masked primes above chance-level (and, hence, the level
511 of awareness of the primes), prime shape discrimination responses from the prime visibility task
512 were transformed into an objective sensibility measure (d'_{obj}) of prime visibility. Once calculated,

⁶ Bayesian tests were conducted using a default scale parameter of 0.707 ($\sqrt{2}/2$) for a Cauchy prior centered on zero.

513 Bayesian one sample t-tests were conducted to assess the degree to which there is evidence to
514 support chance-level ($d' = 0$) prime shape discrimination.

515 In addition, priming effects in the single-task priming block were also analyzed by means of a
516 Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression method (Goldstein et al.,
517 2022; Greenwald et al., 1995). In this method, priming scores are predicted from centered awareness
518 scores⁷, with the regression intercept representing the predicted effect for a given participant whose
519 performance (proportion of correct responses) in the prime shape discrimination task is at chance
520 level (and, therefore, is completely unaware of the primes). To prevent the overestimation of the
521 intercept due to the regression attenuation (Behseta et al., 2009 and Goldstein et al., 2022 for a
522 complete description), we corrected the Greenwald regression procedure employing the Bayesian
523 generative modeling approach developed by (Goldstein et al., 2022), which accounts for
524 measurement error and corrects the bias (overestimation) of the intercept estimation by
525 approximating a posterior distribution for the intercept along with a 95% credible confidence
526 interval, and calculating a BF comparing the evidence for a null model (intercept = 0, absence of
527 subliminal priming effects) against the evidence of a model in which the intercept $\neq 0$ (presence of
528 subliminal priming effects)⁸.

529 The analysis of the multiple-task priming block data also followed a combined approach. First, RTs
530 from trials in which participants gave PAS-1 reports were sent to a Bayesian paired samples t-test
531 comparing congruent vs incongruent conditions⁹. Second, RT data (unfiltered) were sent to a
532 Bayesian paired samples t-test comparing congruent vs incongruent trials following the same
533 procedure outlined for the single-task priming block. In this case, the objective sensibility measure
534 (d'_{obj}) of prime visibility necessary to assess the degree of awareness of the primes during the
535 multiple-task priming block, was calculated based on the responses to the prime shape

⁷ In this method, the proportion of correct responses (p-correct) in the prime shape discrimination task is employed as awareness score. As the expected chance-level performance in a two alternative discrimination task is 0.5, centered awareness scores were computed by subtracting 0,5 to the proportion of correct responses in the task for each participant. Thus, those participants that performed at chance-level have a centered score of 0.

⁸ See Goldstein et al. (2022) and Jimenez et al. (2023) for a detailed explanation on the Bayesian method employed in the regression analysis.

⁹ Initially, RT data in the multiple-task block were intended to be analysed by means of a 2 x 4 repeated measures Bayesian ANOVA with congruency (congruent vs incongruent) and PAS (1: No perception; 2: Weak perception; 3: Almost clear perception, and 4: Clear perception) as within-subjects factors. However, considering the small datasets for PAS-3 and PAS-4 conditions in the global priming experiments, the limited number of participants that would entered the Bayesian ANOVA after listwise deletion due to missing values, especially PAS-2, PAS-3, and PAS-4, and also that the main objective of the study was to explore the priming effects in the absence of awareness, only the individual mean RT data for PAS-1 reports (no perception of the primes) finally entered this analysis.

536 discrimination task performed during this block (see 2.4 section). Once d'_{obj} was calculated,
537 Bayesian one sample t-tests were conducted (in the same way described for the simple-task priming
538 block) to assess the degree to which there is evidence to support chance-level ($d' = 0$) prime shape
539 discrimination. Third, priming effects in the multiple-task priming block were analyzed by means
540 of the same Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression described for the
541 single-task priming block.

542 To further deepen into the unconscious processing of the primes, data from the objective prime
543 shape discrimination task, and prime subjective visibility judgment using the PAS scale in both the
544 multiple-task and the visibility block, were subjected to a general recognition theory (GRT) model-
545 based analysis of the association between awareness and the perceptual processing of the primes
546 (Pournaghдали et al., 2023). This model was then employed to build sensitivity vs awareness (SvA)
547 curves, to characterize the relationship between the perceptual processing of the primes (sensitivity
548 to discriminate the shape of the primes) and the level of awareness¹⁰. Specifically, the data from the
549 prime visibility block were fitted to a two-dimensional GRT model (GRT with individual
550 differences, or GRT-wIND; Ashby & Soto, 2015; Pournaghдали et al., 2023). To ensure that the
551 selected model was the best fit for the data without overfitting, we followed the procedure previously
552 employed by Pournaghдали et al. (2023) and fitted 16 versions of the model using maximum
553 likelihood estimation¹¹. Then we conducted the model selection using the Akaike information
554 criterion (AIC) and chose the best model among the candidates. Once the best GRT model was
555 selected, two values were computed in order to construct the SvA curves: (1) the likelihood that no
556 stimulus was presented over the likelihood that a stimulus was presented, given a particular value
557 in the awareness distribution (i.e., the relative likelihood of no awareness or RLNA), and (2) the
558 conditional sensitivity (d'_{cond}), or the d' computed from the unidimensional normal distribution of

¹⁰ To adapt the PAS scale used in our study to the 2x2 two-dimensional space of the GRT, we collapsed the 4 possible visibility judgments of the PAS scale into two categories namely: unseen (PAS-1) and seen (PAS-2, 3 and 4). Note that this is a quite conservative awareness criterion, as we consider as unaware trials only those in which participants reported no perception at all. To avoid assuming any conscious trial as an unconscious one, PAS-2 judgments were considered as conscious trials, even though this judgement was reserved for situations where, despite having seen something, none of the relevant characteristics of the stimulus could be identified.

¹¹ Model estimation started with a full model in which all parameters were fitted to the data. Then we sequentially constrained the model by fixing the following parameters: (1) All variances were fixed, (2) it was assumed that decisions about the identity of the prime (square or diamond) were not influenced by the level of awareness of the primes, (3) it was assumed that decisions about the awareness of the primes were not influenced by their identity (square or diamond), and (4) it was assumed that the distribution of awareness judgments for a given stimulus was not influenced by the identity of that stimulus. These constraints and their combinations were combined to construct 16 different models that were then compared (see Pournaghдали et al., 2023 for a detailed explanation).

559 square and diamond primes, conditional on a value of the awareness dimension. 95% confidence
560 intervals were obtained by simulating 1,000 data samples from the best GRT model obtained in the
561 previous step. This resulted in a distribution function for SvA curves, and the limits for the
562 confidence intervals were taken from the percentiles of this function. Once the SvA curves and their
563 respective confidence intervals were constructed, they allowed us to evaluate the dependence of the
564 visual processing of the primes from awareness.

565 Finally, to investigate to what extent both objective and subjective prime awareness measures
566 obtained during the multiple-task block (online measures) and the prime visibility block (offline
567 measures) converge, we compared them by transforming both to a common sensitivity measure (d')
568 following and adapting the procedure depicted by Szczepanowski and Pessoa (2007) and previously
569 used by Jimenez et al. (2023). In this method, sensitivity for the objective measures of prime visibility
570 (d'_{obj}) was calculated for each participant by treating one level (e.g., square primes) as the signal and
571 the other level (e.g., diamond primes) as noise during the objective prime shape discrimination tasks
572 performed in the multiple-task priming block and the prime visibility block. On the other hand, d' for
573 the subjective measures (d'_{subj}) was calculated by assuming that trials in which the prime was
574 presented, and participants indicated being aware of it ($PAS = 2, 3$ and 4) correspond to “hits”,
575 whereas trials in which the prime was not presented (catch trials) and participants indicated being
576 aware of its presentation were considered “False alarms”. This allowed us to compare prime
577 awareness estimations derived from objective (d'_{obj}) and subjective (d'_{subj}) measures within a
578 common signal detection theory (SDT) framework, as well as to analyze possible differences between
579 the objective and subjective judgments given in the multiple-task priming block and the prime
580 visibility block due to the different requirements of the tasks. To analyze to what extent objective and
581 subjective measures differ within the same task, and the possible effect of the different tasks on the
582 sensitivity measures, a 2×2 repeated measures Bayesian ANOVA with block (multiple-task priming
583 block, prime visibility block) and d' -type (objective vs subjective) as within-subjects factors was
584 conducted. Bayesian Model Averaging (Wagenmakers et al., 2018; Haldane 1932; Hoeting, Madigan,
585 Raftery, & Volinsky, 1999) was computed to compare models that contain a specific effect to
586 equivalent models without the effect. In addition, we performed Bayesian correlations between
587 sensitivity measures to analyze the degree to which d'_{obj} and d'_{subj} were related within the same task
588 and whether a given sensitivity measure was consistent across the different blocks, particularly we
589 were interested in the correlation between the same measure across different blocks, and the
590 correlation between different measures within the same block.

591 **3. Results**

592 All the tests conducted below are available at the Open Science Repository
593 <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/G3AKU> (see also Supplementary Materials).

594 **3.1 Experiment 1: global priming SOA 40 ms**

595 Twenty-three participants took part in Experiment 1: 16 women, age range = 43 ($M = 30.64$, $SD =$
596 11.93). The number of participants that took part in the experiment was calculated by monitoring the
597 Bayes factor (BF) in the regression analysis (Goldstein et al., 2022), following a mixed Bayesian
598 stopping rule (see section 2.1 for a detailed description). Two participants were replaced due to their
599 low accuracy levels ($< 75\%$) in the multiple-task block. Four participants were replaced due to their
600 incorrect use of the PAS scale ($>10\%$ of “clear perception” reports in the catch trials in either the
601 multiple-task or visibility blocks). Participants’ accuracy in the probe discrimination task was very
602 high (single-task; Congruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.14$, Incongruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.16$; multiple-task;
603 Congruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.16$, Incongruent: $M = .96$, $SD = 0.19$), so only RTs data were analyzed.

604 *Single-task block analyses*

605 First, and following the classical dissociation paradigm (Reingold & Merikle, 1988) we performed a
606 Bayesian paired samples t-test on the individual mean RTs comparing congruent and incongruent
607 trials. The analysis showed strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 39.336$, error % = 4.5×10^{-4}) favoring the
608 existence of a priming effect by the global shape. The RTs obtained in the single task (Congruent: M
609 = 517 ms, $SE = 9.9$ ms; Incongruent: $M = 526$ ms, $SE = 10.4$ ms) were 39.95 times more likely under
610 the alternative hypothesis (i.e., faster RTs in the congruent relative to incongruent trials). See **Figure**
611 **3** and **Table 2**.

612
 613 **Figure 3.** Priming effects (Incongruent – Congruent) in both the single-task priming block, the dual-task
 614 priming block (unfiltered), and the dual-task priming block (filtered by PAS1). Error bars represent standard
 615 error (SE) of the mean.
 616

617 **Table 2.** Mean (M) and standard error (SE) for RTs (ms) in congruent and incongruent conditions in the single-
 618 task priming block, multiple-task priming block (unfiltered), and the multiple-task priming block (filtered by
 619 PAS1) across all four experiments.

Task	RT			
	Congruent		Incongruent	
	M	SE	M	SE
Single				
Global 40 ms	518	9.9	527	10.4
Global 53 ms	548	14.3	554	12.7
Local 40 ms	520	13.3	519	13.6
Local 53 ms	569	20.9	565	20
Multiple				
Global 40 ms	780	42.4	786	43.5
Global 53 ms	859	46.3	870	46.4
Local 40 ms	858	46.2	888	53
Local 53 ms	951	53	983	60.3
Multiple PAS-1				
Global 40 ms	765	40	770	40.7

Global 53 ms	852	46.1	877	49.9
Local 40 ms	814	41.15	828	42.73
Local 53 ms	957	64.1	889	53.15

620 To analyze the extent to which participants were unaware of the primes according to an objective
621 measure of discriminability, responses to the prime shape discrimination task during the visibility
622 block ($M = .55$, $SE = 0.023$) were transformed into a d'_{obj} sensibility measure ($M = 0.32$, $SE = 0.142$)
623 (Green & Swets, 1966; Tanner & Swets, 1954). Mean d'_{obj} scores were then sent to a Bayesian one
624 sample t-test. Results provided moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 3.451$, error % = 7.435×10^{-5}) favoring
625 group visibility being above chance level. Data were 3.45 times more likely under the alternative
626 hypothesis ($d'_{obj} > 0$) than under the null hypothesis ($d'_{obj} = 0$)

627 Last, RT data from the single task were also analyzed employing the Bayesian generative modelling
628 correction to the Greenwald regression method (Greenwald et al., 1995) developed by Goldstein et
629 al. (2022). After fitting the regression model, we found moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.282$ C.I. = 7.928
630 $\times 10^{-5}/0.019$) against a priming effect by the global shape, indicating that the data were 3.54 times
631 more likely under the null model in which the intercept = 0 (no subliminal priming effect) compared
632 to a model drawn from a wide normal distribution (see **Figure 4A**).

633
634 **Figure 4.** Depiction of the Bayesian correction to Greenwald regression in Experiment 1 (Global SOA 40) in
635 the single (A) and multiple (B) tasks. Each circle represents the participant estimated true score. The x-axis
636 represents the centered awareness score, the y-axis represents the estimated effect (incongruent – congruent
637 conditions). The intercept is the expected performance for completely unaware participants.

638 *Multiple-task block analyses*

639 During the multiple-task priming block participants performed three different tasks: (1) a probe
640 discrimination task already performed in the single-task block; (2) a prime shape discrimination task;

641 and (3) a prime visibility judgment using the PAS scale (see section 2.4 for a detailed description).
 642 PAS reports distribution was as follows: PAS-1 (no perception of the prime) was reported on 70,5%
 643 of the trials, PAS-2 (weak perception) on 19,8% of the trials, PAS-3 (almost clear perception) on
 644 8,4% of the trials, and PAS-4 (clear perception) on 1,4% of the trials (see **Table 3**).

PAS	Experiment								
	Block	Global 40 ms		Global 53 ms		Local 40 ms		Local 53 ms	
		M	SE	M	SE	M	SE	M	SE
Multiple-task									
1	70.5	6	65	6.9	52.7	6.3	51.4	8.4	
2	19.8	4	22	4.6	21.7	3	19	4	
3	8.4	2.6	7.6	2.8	14.8	3.3	12.6	3.4	
4	1.4	1.1	5.4	3.7	10.8	3.7	17	5.6	
Prime Visibility									
1	64.1	6.5	52.3	7.6	17.2	5.1	18.8	5.6	
2	18.7	3.4	25.2	4.1	20.9	3.6	22.2	5.4	
3	11.2	2.7	16.3	4.4	24.9	4.2	22.1	4.7	
4	6	2.9	6.2	3.3	37	7.5	36.9	7.5	

645 **Table 3.** Mean (M) and standard error (SE) for PAS reports (%) in the multiple-task priming block and the
 646 prime visibility block across all four experiments.

647 First, and given that in the multiple-task block participants performed both the probe discrimination
 648 task and the prime shape discrimination task, we first analyzed RT data following the classical
 649 dissociation paradigm (Reingold & Merikle, 1988) already employed for the single task. We
 650 performed a Bayesian paired samples t-test on the individual mean RTs comparing congruent and
 651 incongruent conditions in all trials. The analysis showed anecdotal evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.716$, error %
 652 = 0.007) favoring the absence of a priming effect by the global shape. The RTs obtained in the
 653 multiple task (Congruent: $M = 780$ ms, $SE = 42.36$ ms; Incongruent: $M = 786$ ms, $SE = 43.48$ ms)
 654 were 1.39 times more likely under the null hypothesis (i.e., no differences in RTs between congruent
 655 and incongruent conditions). See **Figure 3** and **Table 2**.

656 Responses to the prime shape discrimination task during the multiple-task block ($M = .51$, $SE = 0.01$)
 657 were transformed into a d'_{obj} sensibility measure ($M = 0.073$, $SE = 0.060$). Mean d'_{obj} scores were
 658 then sent to a Bayesian one sample t-test. Results provided anecdotal evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.721$, error
 659 % = 0.010) favoring group visibility being at chance level. Data were 1.386 times more likely under
 660 the null hypothesis ($d'_{obj} = 0$) than under the alternative hypothesis ($d'_{obj} > 0$)

661 Second, the individual mean RT data for PAS-1 reports (no perception of the primes) were sent to a
 662 Bayesian paired samples t-test comparing congruent and incongruent trials. The results showed
 663 moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.380$, error % = 3.835×10^{-6}) against the existence of a congruency effect

664 produced by the global shape in the priming task during the multiple-task block (PAS1-Congruent:
665 $M = 765$ ms, $SE = 40.01$; PAS1-Incongruent: $M = 770$ ms, $SE = 40.68$). See **Tables 2** and **3**, and
666 **Figure 3**.

667 Multiple-task RT data were also analyzed employing the Bayesian generative modelling correction
668 to the Greenwald regression method developed by Goldstein et al. (2022). During the multiple-task
669 block participants performed a prime shape discrimination task, therefore, we used the data from this
670 task as the awareness scores to predict priming scores in the absence of awareness. The results showed
671 moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.110$, C.I -0.027/0.092) against a priming effect by the global shape. Data
672 were 9.09 times more likely under the null model (intercept = 0, no subliminal priming effect)
673 compared to a model drawn from a wide normal distribution (see **Figure 4B**).

674 **3.2 Experiment 2: global priming SOA 53 ms**

675 Twenty participants took part in Experiment 1: 16 women, age range = 39 ($M = 30.95$, $SD = 12$). Six
676 participants were replaced due to their incorrect use of the PAS scale (>10% of “clear perception”
677 reports in the catch trials in either the multiple-task or visibility blocks). Participants’ accuracy in the
678 probe discrimination task was very high (single-task; Congruent: $M = .98$, $SD = 0.04$, Incongruent:
679 $M = .98$, $SD = 0.05$; multiple-task; Congruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.03$, Incongruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.02$),
680 so only RTs data were analyzed.

681 *Single-task block analyses*

682 Bayesian paired samples t-test on the individual mean RTs comparing congruent and incongruent
683 trials showed anecdotal evidence ($BF_{10} = 2.254$, error % = 7.170×10^{-5}) favoring the existence of a
684 priming effect by the global shape. The RTs obtained in the single task (Congruent: $M = 548$ ms, SE
685 = 14.29; Incongruent: $M = 554$ ms, $SE = 12.72$ ms) were 2.25 times more likely under the alternative
686 hypothesis (faster RTs in the congruent relative to incongruent trials). See **Figure 3** and **table 2**.

687 Bayesian one sample t-test performed on the transformed responses (d'_{obj} , $M = 0.52$, $SE = 0.212$) to
688 the prime shape discrimination task during the visibility block ($M = .59$, $SE = 0.034$), provided
689 moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 4.684$, error % = 5.462×10^{-5}) favoring group visibility being above
690 chance level. Data were 4.68 times more likely under the alternative hypothesis ($d'_{obj} > 0$) than under
691 the null hypothesis ($d'_{obj} = 0$)

692 Last, after fitting the Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression, we found
693 moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.251$, C.I = -0.001/0.024) against a priming effect by the global shape,
694 indicating that the data were 3.98 times more likely under the null model in which the intercept = 0

695 (no subliminal priming effect) compared to a model drawn from a wide normal distribution (see
696 **Figure 5A**).

697
698 **Figure 5.** Depiction of the Bayesian correction to Greenwald regression in Experiment 2 (Global SOA 53) in
699 the single (A) and multiple (B) tasks. Each circle represents the participant estimated true score. The x-axis
700 represents the centered awareness score, the y-axis represents the estimated effect (incongruent – congruent
701 conditions). The intercept is the expected performance for completely unaware participants.

702 *Multiple-task block analyses*

703 During the multiple-task block PAS reports distribution was as follows: PAS-1 was reported on 65%
704 of the trials, PAS-2 on 22% of the trials, PAS-3 on 7.6% of the trials, and PAS-4 on 5.4% of the trials
705 (see **Table 3**).

706 The Bayesian paired samples t-test on the individual mean RTs comparing congruent and incongruent
707 conditions in all trials showed moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.109$, error % = 3.005×10^{-4}) favoring the
708 absence of a priming effect by the global shape. The RTs obtained in the multiple task (Congruent:
709 $M = 859$ ms, $SE = 46.27$; Incongruent: $M = 870$ ms, $SE = 46.40$) were 9.17 times more likely under
710 the null hypothesis (i.e., no differences in RTs between congruent and incongruent conditions). See
711 **Figure 3** and **Table 2**.

712 Bayesian one sample t-test performed on the transformed responses (d'_{obj} , $M = 0.23$, $SE = 0.16$) to
713 the prime shape discrimination task during the visibility block ($M = .53$, $SE = 0.02$) provided
714 anecdotal evidence ($BF_{10} = 1.054$, error % = 0.010) favoring group visibility being at chance level.
715 Data were 1.05 times more likely under the alternative hypothesis ($d'_{obj} > 0$) than under the null
716 hypothesis ($d'_{obj} = 0$).

717 Individual mean RT data for PAS-1 reports were sent to a Bayesian paired samples t-test comparing
718 congruent and incongruent trials. The results showed anecdotal evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.510$, error % =

719 1.620×10^{-6}) against the existence of a congruency (priming) effect produced by the global shape in
720 the priming task during the multiple-task block (PAS1-Congruent: $M = 852$ ms, $SE = 46.13$; PAS1-
721 Incongruent: $M = 877$ ms, $SE = 49.92$). See **Table 2** and **Figure 3**.

722 Last, the results from the Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression
723 showed moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.1538053$, C.I -0.039954/0.028277) against a priming effect by
724 the global shape. Data were 6.5 times more likely under the null model (intercept = 0, no subliminal
725 priming effect) compared to a model drawn from a wide normal distribution (see **Figure 5B**).

726 **3.3 Experiment 3: local priming SOA 40 ms**

727 Twenty-six participants took part in Experiment 3 (24 women, age range = 38 years; $M = 28.57$; SD
728 = 11.51). Two participants were replaced due to an incorrect use of the PAS scale (i.e., more than
729 10% “clear perception” reports for catch trials in either the multiple-task or the prime visibility
730 blocks). Participants responses were extremely accurate (single-task; Congruent: $M = .99$, $SD = 0.09$,
731 Incongruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.13$; dual-task; Congruent: $M = .98$, $SD = 0.12$, Incongruent: $M = .98$,
732 $SD = 0.12$), so only RT data were analyzed.

733 *Single-task block analyses*

734 A Bayesian paired samples t-test was performed comparing individual mean RTs for congruent vs
735 incongruent trials. The results showed moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.166$, error % = 9.982×10^{-5})
736 against a priming effect by the local elements (Congruent: $M = 520$ ms, $SE = 13.29$; Incongruent: M
737 = 519 ms, $SE = 13.59$; see **Table 2** and **Figure 3**).

738 Prime detection responses from the prime visibility task ($M = .83$, $SE = 0.03$) were transformed into
739 a sensibility measure (d'_{obj} ; $M = 2.551$, $SE = 0.31$; see **Table 3**) and sent to a Bayesian one sample t-
740 test. The results ($BF_{10} = 1.546 \times 10^6$, error % = 3.652×10^{-9}) indicated very strong evidence favoring
741 group visibility of the primes being above chance level ($d'_{obj} > 0$).

742 Last, the results from the Bayesian generative regression model showed strong evidence ($BF_{10} =$
743 0.086 , C.I -0.023 / 0.013) against a priming effect by the local elements. Data were 11.66 times more
744 likely under the null hypothesis where the intercept of the regression model is set to 0 (no subliminal
745 priming effect), compared to the alternative hypothesis (indicating a subliminal effect) (see **Figure**
746 **6A**).

Depiction of the Bayesian correction to Greenwald regression

747

748 **Figure 6.** Depiction of the Bayesian correction to Greenwald regression in Experiment 3 (Local SOA 40) in
749 the single (A) and multiple (B) tasks. Each circle represents the participant estimated true score. The x-axis
750 represents the centered awareness score, the y-axis represents the estimated effect (incongruent – congruent
751 conditions). The intercept is the expected performance for completely unaware participants.

752 *Multiple-task block analyses*

753 The multiple-task priming block distribution of PAS reports was as follows: PAS1 (no perception of
754 the prime) was reported on 52.7% of the trials, PAS2 (weak perception) on 21.7% of the trials, PAS3
755 (almost clear perception) on 14.8% of the trials, and PAS4 (clear perception) on 10.8% of the trials
756 (see **Table 3**).

757 The results from the Bayesian paired samples t-test on the individual mean RTs comparing congruent
758 and incongruent conditions in all trials indicated moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 3.557$, error % = 8.812
759 $\times 10^{-5}$) favoring the existence of a priming effect by the local elements. The RTs obtained in the
760 multiple task (Congruent: $M = 858$ ms, $SE = 46.23$; Incongruent: $M = 888$ ms, $SE = 53$) were 3.557
761 times more likely under the alternative hypothesis (i.e., existence of a priming effect by the local
762 elements). See **Figure 3** and **Table 2**.

763 Responses to the prime shape discrimination task during the multiple-task block ($M = .60$, $SE = 0.02$)
764 were transformed into a d'_{obj} sensibility measure ($M = 0.575$, $SE = 0.151$) and sent to a Bayesian one
765 sample t-test. Results provided very strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 81.106$, error % = 1.522×10^{-5}) favoring
766 group visibility of the primes being above chance level. Data were 81.10 times more likely under the
767 alternative hypothesis ($d'_{obj} > 0$).

768 The Bayesian paired samples t-test performed on mean RT data comparing congruent and incongruent
769 trials for PAS-1 reports, showed anecdotal evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.846$, error % = 4.291×10^{-5}) against
770 the existence of a congruency effect produced by the local elements in the priming task during the

771 multiple-task block (PAS1-Congruent: $M = 814$ ms, $SE = 41.15$; PAS1-Incongruent: $M = 827$ ms, SE
772 $= 42.73$). See **Table 2**, and **Figure 3**.

773 Last, the results from the Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression
774 showed strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.072$, C.I $-0.021/0.017$) against a priming effect by the local
775 elements. Data were 13.81 times more likely under the null model (intercept = 0, no subliminal
776 priming effect) compared to a model drawn from a wide normal distribution (see **Figure 6B**).

777 **3.4 Experiment 4: local priming SOA 53 ms**

778 Twenty-three participants took part in Experiment 4 (18 women, age range = 37 years; $M = 32.23$;
779 $SD = 11.98$). Two participants were replaced due to an incorrect use of the PAS scale (i.e., more than
780 10% “clear perception” reports for catch trials in either the multiple-task or the prime visibility
781 blocks). Participants responses were extremely accurate (single-task; Congruent: $M = .98$, $SD = 0.02$,
782 Incongruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.03$; dual-task; Congruent: $M = .98$, $SD = 0.03$, Incongruent: $M = .98$,
783 $SD = 0.02$), so only RT data were analyzed.

784 *Single-task block analyses*

785 The Bayesian paired samples t-test performed on the individual mean RTs comparing congruent and
786 incongruent trials showed moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.120$, error % = 0.001) against the existence
787 of a priming effect by the local elements. The RTs obtained in the single task (Congruent: $M = 568$
788 ms, $SE = 20.85$ ms; Incongruent: $M = 565$ ms, $SE = 20.02$) were 8.33 times more likely under the null
789 hypothesis (i.e., no differences between RTs in congruent and incongruent trials). See **Figure 3** and
790 **Table 2**.

791 The Bayesian one sample t-test performed on the transformed responses (d'_{obj} , $M = 2.105$, $SE = 0.318$)
792 to the prime shape discrimination task during the visibility block ($M = .79$, $SE = 0.034$) provided very
793 strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 30866.403$ error % = 5.742×10^{-7}) favoring group visibility being above
794 chance level. Data were 30866 times more likely under the alternative hypothesis ($d'_{obj} > 0$) than
795 under the null hypothesis ($d'_{obj} = 0$).

796 Last, the results from the Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression
797 showed strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.076$, C.I = $-0.028/0.018$) against a priming effect by the global
798 shape, indicating that the data were 14.29 times more likely under the null model (no subliminal
799 priming effect) compared to a model drawn from a wide normal distribution (see **Figure 7A**).

Depiction of the Bayesian correction to Greenwald regression

800

801 **Figure 7.** Depiction of the Bayesian correction to Greenwald regression in Experiment 1 (Local SOA 53) in
 802 the single (A) and multiple (B) tasks. Each circle represents the participant estimated true score. The x-axis
 803 represents the centered awareness score, the y-axis represents the estimated effect (incongruent – congruent
 804 conditions). The intercept is the expected performance for completely unaware participants.

805 *Multiple-task block analyses*

806 The distribution of PAS reports during the multiple-task priming block was as follows: PAS1 (no
 807 perception of the prime) was reported on 51.4% of the trials, PAS2 (weak perception) on 19% of the
 808 trials, PAS3 (almost clear perception) on 12.6% of the trials, and PAS4 (clear perception) on 17% of
 809 the trials (see **Table 3**).

810 The Bayesian paired samples t-test performed on the individual mean RTs comparing congruent and
 811 incongruent conditions in all trials, indicated anecdotal evidence ($BF_{10} = 2.882$, error % = 9.054×10^{-5})
 812 favoring the existence of a priming effect by the local elements. The RTs obtained (Congruent: M
 813 = 951 ms, $SE = 53.03$; Incongruent: $M = 982$ ms, $SE = 60.02$) were 2.88 times more likely under the
 814 alternative hypothesis (i.e., existence of a priming effect by the local elements). See **Figure 3** and
 815 **Table 2**.

816 The Bayesian one sample t-test performed on the transformed responses (d'_{obj} , $M = 0.748$, $SE = 0.241$)
 817 to the prime shape discrimination task during the visibility block ($M = .62$, $SE = 0.03$) provided strong
 818 evidence ($BF_{10} = 16.938$, error % = 8.330×10^{-4}) favoring group visibility of the primes being above
 819 chance level. Data were 16.94 times more likely under the alternative hypothesis ($d'_{obj} > 0$), compared
 820 to the null hypothesis ($d'_{obj} = 0$).

821 The results from the Bayesian paired samples t-test comparing PAS-1 congruent and incongruent trials
 822 showed anecdotal evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.533$, error % = 5.756×10^{-6}) against the existence of a priming
 823 effect produced by the local elements in the priming task during the multiple-task block (PAS1-

824 Congruent: $M = 957$ ms, $SE = 64.10$; PAS1-Incongruent: $M = 889$ ms, $SE = 53.15$). See **Tables 2**,
825 and **Figure 3**. However, the variability of the PAS reports in the present SOA condition (local priming
826 SOA 53 ms) resulted in five participants having less than ten PAS-1 reports (two participants had no
827 PAS-1 incongruent trials), what in turn led to highly unreliable RTs. Therefore, the results for PAS-
828 1 RTs should be interpreted with caution.

829 Last, The Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression showed moderate
830 evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.110$, C.I -0.029/0.0772) against a non-conscious priming effect by the local
831 elements. Data were 9.07 times more likely under the null model (intercept = 0, no subliminal priming
832 effect) compared to a model drawn from a wide normal distribution (see **Figure 7B**).

833 **3.5. General Recognition Theory based analyses: Sensitivity vs Awareness (SvA)**

834 As described in the Data Analysis section, data from the prime shape discrimination task and
835 subjective prime visibility judgments during the multiple-task and visibility blocks were subjected
836 to a GRT model-based analysis of the association between awareness (PAS scale) and the
837 perceptual processing of the prime (prime shape discrimination task). The obtained model was
838 employed to build a SvA curve to characterize the relationship between the perceptual processing of
839 the primes (d'_{obj} for the shape discrimination) and the level of awareness (see section 2.4 for the full
840 description of this analysis).

841 *Experiment 1: global priming SOA 40 ms*

842 In the multiple-task block of Experiment 1, after fitting all the sixteen models (the full model along
843 with those derived from the constraints imposed to the full model and their combinations), the model
844 assuming equal variances and perceptual and decisional separability for awareness was found to be
845 the one that represented the data the best (see **Table S1** and **Figure S1** in the supplementary
846 materials), accounting for the 97.85% of the observed response proportions. The main results are
847 depicted in **Figure 8A**. The x-axis represents the RLNA, and the y-axis represents d'_{obj} computed
848 from the prime shape discrimination task during the multiple-task block. The blue dotted vertical line
849 represents the objective criterion of an ideal observer which divides the x-axis into a region of high
850 likelihood of awareness (left), and a region of low likelihood of awareness to the right. The green
851 dotted vertical lines depict the actual criteria set by each participant. The pattern of the SvA curve
852 (see Pournaghdali et al., 2023 for a complete description of the relationship between different patterns
853 of SvA curves and the awareness/perceptual processing interaction) indicates that perceptual
854 processing of shape is dependent of awareness, as sensitivity drops when RLNA increases. However,
855 there is evidence of nonconscious processing of the global shape: the SvA curve is above a d'_{obj} of

856 zero when it crosses the optimal criterion (blue dotted line) into the region of low likelihood of
857 awareness.

858
859 **Figure 8.** Sensitivity vs. awareness (SvA) curves obtained during the Experiment 1 (Global SAO 40 during
860 the multiple-task (A) and visibility blocks (B). The solid red line represents the SvA curve obtained from the
861 best adjusted model, and the lighter red bands represents 95% confidence intervals. The dotted blue line
862 separates regions of relative high likelihood of awareness to the left, and relative low regions o awareness to
863 the right. The dotted green lines are the estimated bounds for each participant. The horizontal black dotted line
864 represents zero sensitivity ($d' = 0$) in the prime shape discrimination task.

865 In the visibility block the model assuming equal variances and perceptual and decisional
866 separability for awareness was found to be the one that represented the data the best (see **Table S2**
867 and **Figure S2** in the supplementary materials), accounting for the 95.71% of the observed response
868 proportions. As in the multiple-task analysis, the pattern of the SvA curve indicates (1) that
869 perceptual processing of shape is dependent of awareness, and (2) that there is evidence of
870 nonconscious processing of the global shape: the SvA curve is above a d'_{obj} of zero when RLNA is
871 high (see **Figure 8B**).

872 *Experiment 2: global priming SOA 53 ms*

873 In the multiple-task block of Experiment 2, the model assuming perceptual and decisional separability
 874 for awareness was found to be the one that represented the data the best (see **Table S3** and **Figure S3**
 875 in the supplementary materials), accounting for the 95.5% of the observed response proportions. The
 876 main results are depicted in Figure 7A. The pattern of the SvA curve indicates: (1) that perceptual
 877 processing of shape is independent of awareness, and (2) the existence of nonconscious processing
 878 of the global shape, as the SvA curve is above $d'_{obj} = 0$ when it crosses the optimal criterion (blue
 879 dotted line) into the high RLNA region (see **Figure 9A**).

880
 881 **Figure 9.** Sensitivity vs. awareness (SvA) curves obtained during the Experiment 2 (Global SOA 53) during
 882 the multiple-task (A) and visibility blocks (B). The solid red line represents the SvA curve obtained from the
 883 best adjusted model, and the lighter red bands represents 95% confidence intervals. The dotted blue line
 884 separates regions of relative high likelihood of awareness to the left, and relative low regions o awareness to
 885 the right. The dotted green lines are the estimated bounds for each participant. The horizontal black dotted line
 886 represents zero sensitivity ($d' = 0$) in the prime shape discrimination task.

887
 888 Regarding the visibility block, the model assuming equal variances and decisional separability for
 889 awareness was found to be the one that represented the data the best (see **Table S4** and **Figure S4**
 890 in the supplementary materials), accounting for the 97% of the observed response proportions. The
 891 pattern of the SvA curve indicates (1) that perceptual processing of shape is dependent of

892 awareness, and (2) that there is evidence of nonconscious processing of the global shape: the SvA
893 curve is above a d'_{obj} of zero when RLNA is high (see **Figure 9B**).

894 *Experiment 3: local priming SOA 40 ms*

895 The analysis of the multiple-task block of Experiment 3 showed that the model assuming perceptual
896 and decisional separability for awareness was found to be the one that represented the data the best
897 (see **Figure S5** and **Table S5** in the supplementary materials), accounting for the 96.14% of the
898 observed response proportions. The main results are depicted in Figure X-left. The pattern of the SvA
899 curve indicates that the perceptual processing of local elements is dependent of awareness, as
900 sensitivity drops when RLNA increases. However, there is also evidence of nonconscious processing
901 of the local elements: the SvA curve is above a d'_{obj} of zero when it crosses the optimal criterion (blue
902 dotted line) into the region of low likelihood of awareness (see **Figure 10A**).

903
904 **Figure 10.** Sensitivity vs. awareness (SvA) curves obtained during the Experiment 3 (Local SOA 40) during
905 the multiple-task (A) and visibility blocks (B). The solid red line represents the SvA curve obtained from the
906 best adjusted model, and the lighter red bands represents 95% confidence intervals. The dotted blue line
907 separates regions of relative high likelihood of awareness to the left, and relative low regions o awareness to
908 the right. The dotted green lines are the estimated bounds for each participant. The horizontal black dotted line
909 represents zero sensitivity ($d' = 0$) in the prime shape discrimination task

910 On the other hand, in the visibility-block the model assuming decisional separability for awareness
911 was found to be the one that represented the data the best (see **Figure S6** and **Table S6** in the
912 supplementary materials), accounting for the 99.06% of the observed response proportions. The
913 pattern of the SvA curve indicates (1) that perceptual processing of shape is dependent of awareness,
914 and (2) that there is evidence of nonconscious processing of the local elements: the SvA curve is
915 above a d'_{obj} of zero when RLNA is high (see **Figure 10B**).

916 *Experiment 4: local priming SOA 53 ms*

917 In the multiple-task block, the model assuming equal variances along with perceptual and decisional
918 separability for awareness was found to be the one that represented the data the best (see **Figure S7**
919 and **Table S7** in the supplementary materials), accounting for the 98.31% of the observed response
920 proportions. The main results are depicted in Figure X-left. The pattern of the SvA curve indicates
921 that the perceptual processing of local elements is dependent of awareness, as sensitivity drops when
922 RLNA increases. However, there is clear evidence of nonconscious processing of the local elements:
923 the SvA curve is above a d'_{obj} of zero when it crosses the optimal criterion (blue dotted line) into the
924 region of low likelihood of awareness (see **Figure 11A**).

925

926 **Figure 11.** Sensitivity vs. awareness (SvA) curves obtained during the Experiment 4 (Local SOA 53) during
927 the multiple-task (A) and visibility blocks (B). The solid red line represents the SvA curve obtained from the
928 best adjusted model, and the lighter red bands represents 95% confidence intervals. The dotted blue line
929 separates regions of relative high likelihood of awareness to the left, and relative low regions o awareness to
930 the right. The dotted green lines are the estimated bounds for each participant. The horizontal black dotted line
931 represents zero sensitivity ($d' = 0$) in the prime shape discrimination task.

932 Last, the analysis of the visibility-block of Experiment 4 showed that the model assuming equal
933 variances and decisional separability for awareness was found to be the one that represented the data
934 the best (see **Figure S8** and **Table S8** in the supplementary materials), accounting for the 98.49% of
935 the observed response proportions. The pattern of the SvA curve indicates (1) that perceptual
936 processing of shape is dependent of awareness, and (2) that there is evidence of nonconscious
937 processing of the local elements: the SvA curve is above a d'_{obj} of zero when RLNA is high (see
938 **Figure 11B**).

939 **3.6. Prime visibility task: d'_{obj} vs. d'_{subj} comparison**

940 To compare prime awareness estimations derived from objective (prime shape discrimination) and
941 subjective (PAS) tasks along the four experiments, objective and subjective awareness criteria were
942 transformed into a common sensitivity measure (d'). Individual mean d' 's during the dual task
943 ($d'_{obj(multiple-task)}$ and $d'_{subj(multiple-task)}$) and visibility blocks ($d'_{obj(visibility)}$ and $d'_{subj(visibility)}$) in each
944 experiment were sent to a 2 x 2 Bayesian repeated measures ANOVA with Block (single-task,
945 multiple-task) and d' -type (objective, subjective) as within-subject factors, to assess (1) whether
946 prime awareness estimations differed between objective and subjective measures during the same
947 block, and (2) whether prime awareness estimations differed between the dual-task block and the
948 visibility block.

949 Model comparison in both the Global SOA 40 and the Global SOA 53 experiments indicated that the
950 model including Block as main factor explained the data 2.36 (Global SOA 40: Block, $BF_{10} = 10.693$,
951 error % = 1.603; Block + d' -type: $BF_{10} = 4.532$, error % = 3.18) and 3.13 (Global SOA 53: Block,
952 $BF_{10} = 3.047$, error % = 9.814; Block + d' -type: $BF_{10} = 0.970$, error % = 4.181) times better than a
953 model with Block and d' -type as main factors (both against the null model without factors).
954 Averaging the conclusions from each candidate model weighted by that model's posterior plausibility
955 (i.e., Bayesian model averaging) showed moderate evidence in favor of Block differences in d' in the
956 Global SOA 40 experiment (Block, $BF_{incl} = 7.648$), and only anecdotal evidence favoring Block
957 differences in d' in the Global SOA 53 experiment (Block, $BF_{incl} = 2.093$) congruent with the
958 observed overall increase in sensitivity in the visibility block compared to the multiple-task block.

959 Model comparison in the Local SOA 40 experiment showed that a model including Block and d'-
 960 type as main factors and the interaction between Block and d'-type explained the data 5.78 times
 961 better than a model with Block and d'-type as main factors (Block, d'-type and Block x d'-type: BF_{10}
 962 = 3.661×10^7 , error % = 3.279; Block, d'-type: BF_{10} = 6.335×10^6 , error % = 2.798). Bayesian model
 963 averaging showed strong evidence in favor of block differences on d' (Block: BF_{incl} = 1.231×10^7),
 964 congruent with the increased sensitivity in the visibility block already mentioned. The analysis also
 965 showed strong evidence favoring a Block x d'-type interaction (BF_{incl} = 14.020), indicating that
 966 differences between objective and subjective d' measures appeared only in the multiple-task block.

967 Last, in the Local SOA 53 experiment, the model including Block and d'-type as main factors
 968 explained the data 3.62 times better than a model with Block and d'-type as main factors and the
 969 interaction between Block and d'-type (Block, d'-type: BF_{10} = 3.132×10^7 , error % = 4.284; Block,
 970 d'-type and Block x d'-type: BF_{10} = 8.649×10^6 , error % = 2.923;). Bayesian model averaging showed
 971 strong evidence in favor of block differences on d' (Block: BF_{incl} = 2.448×10^6), and strong evidence
 972 favoring a d'-type effect (BF_{incl} = 10.547), indicating that subjective d's were higher compared to
 973 objective d's.

974 Overall, these results seem to be driven by an overall increased visibility of the primes during the
 975 visibility block, compared to the multiple-task priming block, along with a tendency for subjective
 976 measures to be higher than objective measures, more pronounced in the local priming experiments.
 977 (see **Table 3** and **Figure 12**).

978 **Figure 12.** Sensitivity measures (d') obtained during the multiple-task and visibility blocks (d'_{obj} and d'_{subj}).
 979

980 Finally, to analyze the degree to which d'_{obj} and d'_{sub} were related within the same task and whether
981 a given sensitivity measure was consistent across the different blocks, we conducted Bayesian linear
982 correlations between awareness measures within the multiple-task ($d'_{obj(multiple-task)}$ and $d'_{subj(multiple-}$
983 $task)$) and visibility blocks ($d'_{obj(visibility)}$ and $d'_{subj(visibility)}$), and between the same measure across
984 different blocks ($d'_{obj(multiple-task)}$ and $d'_{obj(visibility)}$; $d'_{subj(multiple-task)}$ and $d'_{subj(visibility)}$). The results showed
985 overall strong correlations within measures/between blocks and between measures/within blocks,
986 indicating great consistency across the different measures of awareness collected (see **Table 4** for a
987 summary; see also the supplementary materials for a complete correlation matrix between awareness
988 measures).

Experiment	d' values	Correlation	BF_{10}	Pearson's r
Global SOA 40 ms	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} = 0.073$	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} - d'_{subj(multiple-task)}$	5.259	0.463
	$d'_{obj(visibility)} = 0.319$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	289.221	0.694***
	$d'_{subj(multiple-task)} = 0.151$	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} - d'_{obj(visibility)}$	1865.976	0.757***
	$d'_{subj(visibility)} = 0.392$	$d'_{subj(multiple-task)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	824.921	0.731***
Global SOA 53 ms	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} = 0.230$	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} - d'_{subj(multiple-task)}$	15.906	0.625*
	$d'_{obj(visibility)} = 0.515$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	1916.471	0.814***
	$d'_{subj(multiple-task)} = 0.226$	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} - d'_{obj(visibility)}$	163.048	0.737***
	$d'_{subj(visibility)} = 0.596$	$d'_{subj(multiple-task)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	25258.694	0.869***
Local SOA 40 ms	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} = 0.575$	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} - d'_{subj(multiple-task)}$	56.915	0.622**
	$d'_{obj(visibility)} = 2.551$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	8642.373	0.781***
	$d'_{subj(multiple-task)} = 1.162$	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} - d'_{obj(visibility)}$	203.543	0.674***
	$d'_{subj(visibility)} = 2.609$	$d'_{subj(multiple-task)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	227.081	0.678***
Local SOA 53 ms	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} = 0.748$	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} - d'_{subj(multiple-task)}$	293.053	0.720***
	$d'_{obj(visibility)} = 2.105$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	47.654	0.646**
	$d'_{subj(multiple-task)} = 1.395$	$d'_{obj(multiple-task)} - d'_{obj(visibility)}$	2288.726	0.782***
	$d'_{subj(visibility)} = 2.706$	$d'_{subj(multiple-task)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	9865.952	0.816***

989 **Table 4.** d' values for objective and subjective sensitivity measures of prime shape discrimination. Bayes
990 factor (BF_{10}) and Pearson's correlation coefficients (r) for the relevant comparisons between sensitivity
991 measures across all four experiments. * $BF_{10} > 10$, ** $BF_{10} > 30$, *** $BF_{10} > 100$

992 4. Discussion

993 The present study employed a masked priming design with hierarchical visual stimuli similar to the
994 ones employed by Sabary et al. (2020), and Jimenez et al. (2023) in two different masking conditions
995 (SOA 40 and 53 ms), to explore the relationships between perceptual organization and

996 consciousness, and particularly whether global and local shapes can be unconsciously processed.
 997 To this end, we compared three alternative approaches: the classical dissociation paradigm, and the
 998 two newly proposed Bayesian generative and General Recognition Theory models. Crucially, we
 999 implemented an exhaustive, integrative procedure in which objective and subjective, as well as
 1000 offline and online measures of awareness were combined in a within-subjects design, allowing us a
 1001 thorough comparison of prime sensitivity (d') for the different combinations of awareness
 1002 measures..

1003 Overall, the pattern of results obtained can be summarized around three key points: (1) The classic
 1004 analysis strategies associated to the masked priming paradigm showed mixed evidence regarding
 1005 the unconscious processing of the primes, that seemed to be influenced by the type of priming (local
 1006 vs global) and the way in which awareness measures were collected (online vs offline). Interestingly,
 1007 when a Bayesian generative model (Goldstein et al., 2022) was fitted to the data, any evidence in
 1008 favor of prime related facilitation effects seemed to vanish across all conditions and experiments.
 1009 (2) Conversely, when the unconscious processing of the prime was assessed directly through a
 1010 general recognition theory (GRT) model-based analysis that measured the association between
 1011 awareness and perceptual processing, our results indicated that primes were processed even when
 1012 the relative likelihood of no awareness was high. (3) Finally, when converted to a common
 1013 sensitivity measure (d'), objective and subjective measures of awareness collected during the
 1014 multiple-task (online) and visibility blocks (offline), showed similar values within the same task, a
 1015 high degree of correlation both within and between tasks and, importantly, both were sensitive to
 1016 the differences in prime visibility associated to the attentional variations due to the different task
 1017 demands (an overview of the main results can be found in **Table 5**). Each of these points will be
 1018 discussed in more detail below.

Analysis method	Main results
Classical dissociation paradigm: <i>(Objective awareness measures)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence favoring priming effects for the global shape in Experiments 1 (strong) and 2 (anecdotal) during the single-task block. • Evidence against priming effects for the local elements in Experiments 3 and 4 (moderate) during the single-task block. • No evidence for priming effects for the global shape in Experiments 1 and 2 during the multiple task block • Evidence favoring priming effects for the local elements in Experiments 3 and 4 (moderate) during the multiple-task block. • Increased RT and variability during the multiple-task block compared to the single-task block • All $d' > 0$ except in the multiple-task block of Experiment 1

Perceptual awareness scale (PAS-1): <i>(Subjective awareness measures)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence against the existence of unconscious priming effects for the global shape in the multiple-task block of Experiment 1 (moderate) and 2 (anecdotal) • Evidence against the existence of unconscious priming effects for the local elements in the multiple-task block of Experiment 3 (anecdotal) and 4 (anecdotal). • No evidence of priming effects when only PAS-1 (non-conscious) trials were analyzed
Bayesian regression <i>(Objective awareness measures)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence against the existence of unconscious priming effects for the global shape in the single-task block of Experiment 1 (moderate) and 2 (moderate). • Evidence against the existence of unconscious priming effects for the local elements in the single-task block of Experiment 3 (strong) and 4 (strong). • Evidence against the existence of unconscious priming effects for the global shape in the multiple-task block of Experiment 1 (moderate) and 2 (moderate). • Evidence against the existence of unconscious priming effects for the local elements in the multiple-task block of Experiment 3 (strong) and 4 (moderate).
GRT-based SvA curves <i>(Subjective awareness measures)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greater than 0 sensitivity (d') when RLNA was high (>1) for the global shapes in Experiment 1 (≈ 0.25) and 2 (≈ 0.6) during the multiple-task block • Greater than 0 sensitivity (d') when RLNA was high (>1) for local elements in Experiment 3 (≈ 0.75) and 4 (≈ 1.7) during the multiple-task block • Greater than 0 sensitivity (d') when RLNA was high (>1) for the global shapes in Experiment 1 (≈ 1.25) and 2 (≈ 1.5) during the visibility block • Greater than 0 sensitivity (d') when RLNA was high (>1) for local elements in Experiment 3 (≈ 2.5) and 4 (≈ 2.7) during the visibility block
Objective VS subjective awareness measures comparison <i>(d'_{obj} vs d'_{subj})</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greater d' values (both objective and subjective during the visibility block (full attention to the primes), compared to the multiple-task block (divided attention between primes and probes) in all experiments. • Overall greater d' values when assessed by means of subjective awareness measures, compared to objective awareness measures. • Overall strong correlations between objective (d'_{obj}) and subjective (d'_{subj}) measures of awareness within the same block (multiple-task and visibility blocks respectively) • Overall strong correlations within objective (d'_{obj}) measures of awareness collected in different blocks (multiple-task and visibility blocks respectively) • Overall strong correlations within subjective (d'_{subj}) measures of awareness collected in different blocks (multiple-task and visibility blocks respectively)

1019 **Table 4.** Summary of the results according to the different types of analysis performed

1020 Indeed, when the data were analyzed following the classical masked priming (dissociation)
1021 paradigm (Reingold & Merikle, 1988), we found strong evidence of priming effects for the global
1022 shape in Experiment 1 (SOA-40) during the single-task block, but only anecdotal evidence of
1023 priming effects in Experiment 2 (SOA-53), also during the single-task block. No evidence of
1024 priming effects by the global shape were found in the multiple-task block in the first two
1025 experiments. Interestingly, the pattern of results reversed for the local priming conditions. Moderate
1026 evidence against the existence of a priming effect was found in Experiments 3 (SOA-40) and 4
1027 (SOA-53) in the single-task block, whereas in the multiple-task block, moderate evidence of the
1028 existence of a priming effect was found for both SOA conditions (see **Figure 3** and **Table 2**). This

1029 result has been surprising, since, in line with previous works (Jimenez et al., 2023; Kiefer et al.,
1030 2023), we expected the inclusion of a multiple-task condition (the probe discrimination task plus
1031 the online awareness measures collected in each trial) to interfere with the operations underlying
1032 masked priming, presumably due to the split of attentional resources between the prime and probe
1033 (Ansorge et al., 2011; Avneon & Lamy, 2018; Jimenez et al., 2023; Kiefer et al., 2023). In fact, this
1034 is what seemed to be happening, as evidenced by the substantial increase in the RTs and their
1035 variability during the multiple-task block in all experiments. One tentative explanation for these
1036 conflicting results could arise from the interaction between the greater visibility of the primes during
1037 the local priming conditions (as shown by the higher objective and subjective awareness measures,
1038 see **Figure 12 and Table 3**) and differences in attentional resources devoted to the prime during the
1039 single and the multiple-task blocks. In the global priming conditions (Experiments 1 and 2) the level
1040 of sensitivity (d'_{obj} and $d'_{subj} < 0,5$) to the masked primes during the multiple-task block was very
1041 low, even though the amount of attentional resources devoted to the masked prime task was higher
1042 compared to the single block (where participants simply ignored the prime as it was irrelevant to
1043 the task). In this situation of extremely low prime visibility, the inclusion of the multiple-task
1044 condition would have resulted in a reduction of the resources allocated to the probe discrimination
1045 task, eliminating the congruency effects found during the single task. Conversely, in the local
1046 priming conditions (Experiments 3 and 4) the sensitivity to the prime during the multiple-task block
1047 was remarkably higher compared to the global priming conditions (see **Figure 12 and Table 3**). In
1048 this scenario, the higher visibility of the primes could be responsible for the support found towards
1049 a priming effect in the multiple-task block, as it would exert a stronger effect than the possible
1050 attenuation resulting from the reduced attentional resources to the probe due to the dual task
1051 conditions. Indeed, this is congruent with the vanishing of the priming effects in the local condition
1052 during the multiple-task block when only PAS-1 trials were analyzed (see **Figure 3 and Table 2**),
1053 indicating that the priming effects were driven mostly by conscious trials. Our results are also
1054 congruent with previous studies on the unconscious processing of hierarchical stimuli. For example,
1055 Sabary et al. (2020) found priming effects by the local elements of hierarchical stimuli in a priming
1056 task in which online subjective awareness measures were collected in each trial, but did not found
1057 priming effects by the global shape in the same condition. On the contrary, Jimenez et al. (2023)
1058 found clear priming effects by the global shape in a single-task condition that disappeared when
1059 subjective awareness measures were collected in a trial-by-trial basis (dual-task condition). These
1060 results also emphasize the need for individual difference studies, as there appear to be large
1061 differences in both the unconscious effects found, and the visibility of the masked stimuli among

1062 participants, as can be seen from the individual data in the regression analyses (**Figures 4, 6, 8 and**
1063 **10**, black dots) and the SvA curves (**Figures 5, 7, 9 and 11**, dotted green lines).

1064 As we discussed in the introduction section, classical approaches to the analysis of the unconscious
1065 effects of masked priming designs have faced several challenges. Particularly, when using objective
1066 performance measures of awareness within the classical dissociation paradigm, one might wonder
1067 whether prime related effects might be a consequence of the average level of awareness being above
1068 zero or, even if the level of performance in the awareness measures does not exceeds the chance
1069 level, the effects found are due to some participants whose awareness levels are particularly high
1070 (Rouder et al., 2007; Sandberg et al., 2010; Shanks, 2017; Timmermans & Cleeremans, 2015). An
1071 analogous situation occurs when online subjective measures are collected in each trial. In this case,
1072 priming effects could be derived from trials in which participants were aware of the prime (e.g.,
1073 PAS 2, 3, and 4 reports). In agreement with these concerns, we found that sensitivity levels were
1074 above chance level in all experiments and conditions except for d'_{obj} during the multiple-task block
1075 in the Global SOA-40 experiment (d'_{obj} ranging from 0.07 to 2.11; d'_{subj} ranging from 0.15 to 2.71,
1076 see **Figure 12 and Table 3**). Therefore, to rule out that priming effects found were due to a limited
1077 number of “conscious” participants or “conscious” trials, and at the same time avoiding post-hoc
1078 data selection and potential regression to the mean effects (Rothkirch et al., 2022; Shanks, 2017;
1079 Yaron et al., 2023), we implemented a Bayesian generative regression model recently developed by
1080 Goldstein et al., (2022. This method estimates intercept in a regression model that represents the
1081 priming effect for an ideal observer whose awareness (estimated by the performance achieved in
1082 the objective prime shape discrimination task) is equal to zero. Interestingly, when using this
1083 method, we found moderate to strong evidence favoring the null hypothesis and against the
1084 unconscious processing of the primes in all priming, task and SOA conditions (see **Figures 4, 6, 8,**
1085 **and 10**; and Figures S9 to S16 in the supplementary materials). These results are in line with an
1086 explanation of the priming effects based on a subset of participants that are at least partially aware
1087 of the masked prime, while those who are not have negligible priming effects, an account that has
1088 been defended by some authors in light of the volatility that unconscious priming effects usually
1089 present throughout the scientific literature (Newell & Shanks, 2014; Shanks et al., 2021; Vadillo et
1090 al., 2022). However, it is important to point out that while the regression model estimated for the
1091 multiple-task block was based on an objective-online measure (and, therefore, collected under the
1092 same conditions in which the priming task was performed), the estimated model for the single-task
1093 block was collected during the separate visibility block (objective-offline). Hence, we cannot rule
1094 out that the absence of an unconscious effect showed by the regression model in the single-task

1095 block derives from an overestimation of the level of awareness of the prime during the visibility
1096 block (remember that, in the single-task block, the participants just ignore the prime and focused on
1097 the probe, while in the visibility block participants' attentional resources were fully centered on the
1098 prime). This conclusion is supported by the lower awareness estimations during the multiple-task
1099 block in which attentional resources were split between the prime and the probe. Interestingly, this
1100 brings us to a paradoxical situation within the dissociation paradigm. Either we measure awareness
1101 concurrently with the task, meeting the criterion of immediacy, but compromising the reliability of
1102 the indirect measure of performance and the awareness assessment (Newell & Shanks, 2014). Or,
1103 alternatively, we measure awareness separately, improving reliability but renouncing to the
1104 immediacy criterion and, to some extent, to part of the validity of our measures (Bengson &
1105 Hutchison, 2007; Lähteenmäki et al., 2015; Shanks & John, 1994). This would resemble an
1106 *uncertainty principle* (Heisenberg, 1927) for the study of unconsciousness and exposes the
1107 researchers to an unavoidable dilemma that we will have to deal with in research on this topic.

1108 All the results discussed above rely on the indirect examination of the unconscious perception of
1109 the local elements or the global shape of the stimuli by means of the comparison between congruent
1110 and incongruent prime-probe responses. However, the paradigm implemented in this study also
1111 makes it possible to assess the unconscious processing of the masked stimulus directly, as
1112 participants performed simultaneously an objective prime shape discrimination task and a subjective
1113 visibility judgement using the PAS scale during the multiple-task and the visibility blocks. This
1114 direct evaluation has been employed in previous studies (Heeks & Azzopardi, 2015; Lähteenmäki
1115 et al., 2015; Pournaghdali et al., 2023; Szczepanowski & Pessoa, 2007) and, analogously to the
1116 classical masked priming paradigm, it also involves a dissociation between two different measures.
1117 However, this dissociation now involves a comparison between a subjective awareness report and
1118 the performance in an objective forced-choice task (either detection or discrimination). This change
1119 is not trivial, as it implies a shift in the theoretical assumptions about what constitutes conscious and
1120 unconscious processing. Particularly, we move from using d' in the forced-choice discrimination
1121 task as a measure of awareness (implying that unconscious processing is only possible if $d' = 0$), to
1122 using it as a measure of perceptual processing (implying that a $d' > 0$ followed by a subjective report
1123 of no awareness is necessary to assume unconscious processing of the stimuli). In other words, we
1124 switch from a more conservative objective threshold to a subjective threshold for which unconscious
1125 processing constitutes a state that falls between the two (Cheesman & Merikle, 1984; Heeks &
1126 Azzopardi, 2015; Jimenez et al., 2024; Lamme, 2020; Michel, 2023). To analyze the existence of
1127 unconscious processing under these assumptions, we employed the method developed by

1128 Pournaghdali et al. (2023) based on the GRT framework (see Ashby & Soto, 2015) that we described
1129 in the introduction section. According to the results depicted in **Figures 5, 7, 9 and 11**, the capacity
1130 to discriminate between different shapes at the local and the global level persists in the absence of
1131 awareness, although the strength of the discrimination depends on its level (i.e., as the RLNA of the
1132 stimulus increases, the performance in the prime shape discrimination task decreases). This contrast
1133 with the results obtained using indirect methods to estimate unconscious processing which, after
1134 removing possible conscious effects (either via a regression model or by selecting unconscious
1135 trials), pointed to the absence of unconscious processing of the primes. Nonetheless, the decoupling
1136 between the results obtained through different methodologies is in accordance with the previously
1137 described distinction between objective and subjective awareness thresholds (Merikle et al., 2001).
1138 It is often assumed that the objective threshold is more restrictive than the subjective threshold, and
1139 consequently that it is associated with a more conservative estimate of participant's awareness.
1140 Therefore, the fundamental question is to determine what exactly each of these thresholds is
1141 measuring, a problem that has been heavily debated and is still a matter of discussion (Jimenez et
1142 al., 2024; Michel, 2023; Timmermans & Cleeremans, 2015). One possible solution is to consider
1143 the different thresholds as different stages in the visual processing stream: a *fully unconscious state*,
1144 which refers to stimuli below the objective threshold of visibility (e.g., $d' = 0$); a *subjectively*
1145 *unconscious state* denoting subjectively unseen stimuli (e.g., $d' > 0$ together with a PAS-1 report);
1146 and a *subjectively conscious state* reserved to those stimuli that surpass both thresholds (Lamme,
1147 2020). This classification somewhat resembles the distinction between phenomenal and access
1148 consciousness proposed by Block (2007). In Block's proposal, it could be possible to think about
1149 phenomenal consciousness (a conscious state that cannot be accessed or reported by the subject) as
1150 a different interpretation of the subjectively unconscious state proposed by Lamme (2020). Once
1151 again, the question brings us back to the very definition of awareness and the underlying phenomena
1152 that we are trying to measure, or whether it is possible to have sensitivity at the subject level in the
1153 absence of a *feels like something* experience. A final critical point to note is that the SvA analysis
1154 also showed differences in the strength of the unconscious processing as a function of the type of
1155 task performed. As shown in **Figures 5, 7, 9, and 11**, the discrimination capacity (d') when the
1156 RLNA criterion is crossed (blue dotted line) is higher during the visibility block (right side of the
1157 figures) compared to the multiple-task block (left side). This is consistent with our expectations
1158 about the effect of the level of attention devoted to the primes, and with the differences found in the
1159 common sensitivity measures (d') calculated to compare awareness measures and which will be
1160 discussed in the following paragraphs.

1161 Our last purpose was to compare the distinct types of awareness measures collected according to
1162 the two dimensions proposed at the Introduction: the objective-subjective and the online-offline
1163 axes. To achieve this goal we converted each awareness measure into a common sensitivity metric
1164 (d') derived from the signal detection theory (Kunimoto et al., 2001; Maniscalco & Lau, 2012, 2014;
1165 Szczepanowski & Pessoa, 2007). The results suggest two different but complementary conclusions.
1166 First, online measures tend to give lower estimates of awareness than offline measures, and the same
1167 occurs when comparing objective measures against subjective measures (see **Figure 12** and **Table**
1168 **3**). These results are not surprising as they reflect the differences in the unconscious processing of
1169 the primes between tasks, and emphasize the relevance of the attentional resources devoted to the
1170 processing of the masked stimuli in the emergence of awareness (De Brigard & Prinz, 2010; Koch
1171 & Tsuchiya, 2012) and also in the degree to which unconscious stimuli are processed (Kanai et al.,
1172 2006; Maier & Tsuchiya, 2021; Naccache et al., 2002). They are also in line with the objective and
1173 subjective threshold account that we discussed above (Lamme, 2020), as indicated by the lower
1174 sensitivity values obtained from the objective awareness measures. The second conclusion is
1175 derived from the high correlations found between objective and subjective awareness measures
1176 within the same block, and between the same awareness measures across different blocks. This high
1177 level of correlation indicates that, irrespective of the absolute value of each measure, participants
1178 are highly consistent in their awareness estimation across measures and tasks. Although at first
1179 glance they appear to conflict with the already discussed differences between measures and tasks,
1180 the two results can be easily integrated within a multiple stage processing account (Lamme, 2020).
1181 According to this view, the absolute differences found between measures and task demands would
1182 correspond with the different demands of processing necessary to reach the objective and subjective
1183 awareness threshold, which would also be influenced by the level of attention paid to the stimuli.
1184 On the other hand, the high correlation between measures within the same task and across different
1185 tasks within the same measure, would be interpreted as evidence in favor of their validity, or at least
1186 indicating that the same construct underlies both measures.

1187 In sum, our results indicate that the unconscious processing of the local and/or the global form in
1188 hierarchical stimuli heavily depends on (1) the type of measure collected, (2) how and when the
1189 measure was collected, and (3) the theoretical assumptions under which a given measure is analyzed
1190 and interpreted. However, none of the awareness measures, the methods employed to collect them,
1191 or the analysis strategies conducted, are entirely satisfactory, as all imply the renunciation to some
1192 of the prerequisites needed for a proper measurement of (un)awareness, or the loss of useful
1193 information about the effects associated with the (un)conscious processing of the stimulus.

1194 Therefore, it seems clear that the only way to achieve a better understanding of the mechanisms
1195 underlying conscious and unconscious processing is to conduct an experimental *tour de force*
1196 through different measures and methods, that allow us to integrate the evidence obtained into a
1197 comprehensive framework on how to identify, differentiate and quantify the conscious and the
1198 unconscious.

1199 **Data Availability**

1200 The methods used and the data analyzed in the present study are available in the Open Science
1201 Framework (OSF) repository through the following link:
1202 <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/G3AKU>

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1210

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